

Specialisations:

Trends and Challenges in Conservation-Restoration Education

Index

ENCoRE Programme Surveys. An Overview Wolfgang Baatz	6
Material Science for Conservators -Bridging the Gap Between Science and Conservation-Restoration Practice Nanna Bjerregaard, Julie Nogel Jæger and Cecil Krarup Andersen	14
Master's Degrees as a Tool for the Specialisation of The Conservation and Restoration Profession. The Case of the Escola Superior de Conservació i Restauració de Béns Culturals de Catalunya (ESCRBCC) M. Àngels Balliu Badia, Marta Pérez Azcárate, Ruth Sadurní Codina	24
Toward an Enhanced Definition of the Specialisation Areas for Portuguese Conservators-Restorers David Teves Reis, Luís Pereira, Elis Marçal	39
Generalists versus Specialists: Education and Demands in professional secretary of Conservation-Restoration in Germany Gisela Gulbins, Julia Brandt	51
The Education of Restorers in ICR: Final Intersectoral Trainings for the Convergence of Knowledge Marco Bartolini, Francesca Capanna, Giorgio Sobrà	57
A Discussion About What Specialisation Means Through the Example of Contemporary Art Conservation Clémentine Bollard	69
From Adaptation to the Context of Monuments to Accounting New Media Overview of The Evolution of Specialities of Educational Training at the Conservator Department of the National Institute for Heritage in Paris Amélie Méthivier, Pauline Chassaing	78
Preserving the Past, Shaping the Future: The Conservator's Landscape in Sweden Sara Roberts	82

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20082082](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20082082)

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PREFACE

*The proceedings gathered in this volume offer a set of contributions to one of the most enduring and complex debates in conservation–restoration education and practice: the role, scope, and implications of **specialisations**. As the profession continues to evolve within increasingly demanding cultural, institutional, environmental and technological scenarios, the question of whether higher education should privilege broad-based generalist education and training or more sharply defined specialist pathways has gained renewed relevance. Similar debates occur about professional practice, regarding which principles dictate a conservator-restorer is competent to operate in an ethical, accountable, and autonomous manner in their specialised field. The papers presented at the Specialisations: Trends and Challenges in Conservation-Restoration Education symposium, held in Prague in April 2025, address this topic from a rich diversity of professional, pedagogical, and regional perspectives.*

It all starts with education. Education is the foundation for professional practice, the way it is designed and delivered shapes professional competencies. In turn, professional expertise should nurture education development. Within this debate, the frameworks articulated jointly by ENCoRE (European Network for Conservation-Restoration Education) and E.C.C.O. (European Confederation of Conservator-Restorers' Organisations) remain central reference points. In particular the joint paper on the recognition of the conservator-restorer profession and education (2005) and the E.C.C.O. Professional Guidelines which later evolved into the "Competences to access the conservation-restoration profession" (2011). ENCoRE's ongoing programme surveys (2016–2021) reveal a landscape marked by significant efforts toward transparency, comparability and alignment with Bologna structures, yet also a persistent heterogeneity in

curriculum length, theory–practice ratios, internship recognition, and nomenclature of specialisations. E.C.C.O.'s professional guidelines and competence-based frameworks continue to underpin academic standards and the definition of the conservator-restorer's professional identity and profile, reinforcing a shared foundation of scientific, ethical, and methodological competencies, irrespective of specialisation.

The contributions in this volume illustrate how some training institutions translate these shared principles into concrete educational models, and how national associations and professionals attempt to respond to heritage sector canons and market expectations. Several papers highlight national reforms that have sought to clarify or expand specialisation frameworks following the broadening scope of heritage practice and the market evolution, such as Portugal's 2020 revision of ARP's professional statute — resulting in an updated catalogue of 17 specialisations — and the recent legislative milestone (Decree-Law No. 90/2024) formally recognising the conservator-restorer as the qualified professional responsible for interventions on protected heritage. Similar reflections emerge in Germany, where the tension between institutional needs and labour-market realities underscores the necessity of both broad competencies and advanced specialist expertise, particularly in contexts where small museums or freelance practice demand versatility.

Other contributions illustrate models where specialisation is approached progressively. The Danish example positions material science as a unifying pillar across all specialisations, fostering a shared scientific vocabulary and enhancing interdisciplinary dialogue. Italy's Istituto Centrale per il Restauro shows how a long-established sectoral system addresses heritage standards as well as market demands. Structured around six macro-areas of materials, it has been enriched through cross-curricular, collaborative modules addressing complex, polymaterial contexts, from open-air contemporary art installations to

disaster-response interventions. The French context reveals how early-entry specialisation coexists with new demands: conservation of historic monuments, mural painting, stained glass, and digital media increasingly require expanded or updated specialities, while the conservation of contemporary art challenges traditional definitions by privileging contextual understanding, conceptual analysis, and project management over material-bound expertise.

The contributions also showed that specialisation is not solely a curricular matter but deeply entangled with labour-market structures and prerequisites, professional recognition and regulation, heritage legal frameworks and requirements and sectoral needs. In Sweden, acute shortages in stone, mural, and metal conservation highlight the urgency of expanding training capacities and strengthening links between education, policy and practice. At the same time, the Swedish case reminds us that highly specialised skills thrive best within ecosystems that also value generalist competencies, preventive conservation, administrative expertise, and the ability to navigate increasingly complex procurement and project-management environments. Several papers underscore the importance of transversal skills — communication, decision-making, leadership, interdisciplinary mediation — as essential complements to specialised technical and scientific knowledge.

Across all contributions, a central theme emerges: specialisation and generalisation are not opposing

poles but interdependent dimensions of a profession that must respond to diverse heritage typologies, evolving technologies, heritage legal criteria and societal expectations. While specialised knowledge and skills are indispensable for addressing the growing complexity of materials, technologies, and contexts, a strong common foundation — scientific, ethical, methodological and reflective — is equally essential for ensuring coherence, quality and mobility in the field. The experiences presented here also highlight the importance of lifelong learning, mentoring, knowledge transfer and expertise exchanges, cross-sector collaboration, and research literacy as mechanisms through which individual professionals refine their specialist identities over time.

These proceedings invite readers to consider specialisation not as a fixed label, but as a dynamic process shaped by educational structures, professional practice, and the changing nature of the cultural heritage sector itself. By presenting case studies, reforms, pedagogical innovations and critical reflections from across Europe, these proceedings contribute meaningfully to the collective effort to articulate clear, coherent, and forward-looking pathways for the education, professional practice and recognition of conservator-restorers. In doing so, they reinforce the shared commitment to safeguard the quality, autonomy, and sustainability of the conservation-restoration profession, ensuring that both emerging and established areas of specialisation continue to evolve in response to heritage needs and societal values.

Laura Fuster-López

Laura FUSTER-LÓPEZ
European Network for
Conservation Restoration Education

Elis Marçal

Elis MARÇAL
European Network of
Conservator-Restorers' Organisations

ENCoRE Programme Surveys. An Overview

Wolfgang BAATZ

Academy of Fine Arts (Vienna, Austria)
(Chair of ENCoRE 2010-2023)

* Contact Author: w.Baatz@akbild.ac.at

Over the years, ENCoRE has been collecting a large amount of data concerning structure, resources and content of the programmes of its members. Already at the first preparatory meeting in 1997 (for the founding of ENCoRE in 1998) the institutions participating in that meeting gave a characterization of their programmes. In 2016 at the GA in Cambridge, it was decided to start a programme survey among the ENCoRE members, followed by the request for regular updates at the GA in Turin two years later. Apart from this, already since 2015 each institution applying for membership has to submit the relevant data of their programme in a standard questionnaire.

In 2018 the ENCoRE Board started discussions on the topic of specialization, with the aim to make the CR education landscape more transparent and to enhance mobility. These discussions yielded some ideas on how to present the data, in particular when characterizing the member institutions on the website, including the topic of specialization and the curriculum structure. This paper will show the results of the data collection and reflect upon the discussion process.

At the start of the symposium this paper gives an overview on the surveys ENCoRE has conducted in the period 2016 – 2021. It will show the results of the data collection and reflect upon the discussion process and its aims. Over the years ENCoRE has been collecting a considerable amount of data concerning the structure, the resources and the content of the programmes of its members.

A first overview

A first overview was achieved at the very first ENCoRE preparatory meeting in Dresden in 1997, which was held in preparation of the founding of ENCoRE a year later. In the publication of that very meeting every participating school delivered information on the length and on other data of their programme as well as on the specialisations offered. 28 educational institutions from 16 countries participated, the majority of them became and still are members of ENCoRE.

It has to be taken into account that the Bologna Declaration was signed only in 1999. The pre-Bologna study structures being very diverse, only a few bachelor and master graduates were presented in the

publication, the length of the programmes differed, and the majority finished with a classic degree or a diploma. (Tables 1, 2)

Table 1: ENCoRE preparatory meeting, Dresden 1997, Programme Structure
(participation: 28 schools from 16 countries)

Members	Programme Structure (Semester)	Certificate
7	10	Diploma
4	12	Diploma
1	4 + 4	Candidate, Master
1	6 + 2	Bachelor, Master
1	8 + 1	?
9	8	Diploma
1	6 + 4	Bachelor, Master
3	6	postgraduate
1	4	Master

Table 2: ENCoRE preparatory meeting, Dresden 1997, Total Programme Duration
(participation: 28 schools from 16 countries)

Members	Total Programme Duration (Semester)
2	4
1	6
1	8
18	10
2	11
4	12

ENCoRE Surveys

At the ENCoRE General Assembly (GA) in Cambridge in 2016 it was decided to conduct a programme survey among the ENCoRE members. The decision came after a proposition of the board that each institution applying for membership should submit the relevant data of their programme. A standard questionnaire for the membership application procedure had already been in use since 2015. One of the initial ideas of this programme survey was - among others - to understand the average ratio theory/practice. Two years later, at the GA 2018 in Turin the results of the first survey were presented, and the decision was taken to have the members deliver regular updates before each GA. However, due to the Covid events, the next survey was started only prior to the GA in November 2020. In the first survey it had turned out that it was very difficult to get detailed data on the staff, due to the large variation of contract types and duties in the different institutions. The 2020 survey was therefore modified to meet this challenge. As it was sent out rather short time before the (online) GA, some responses to the survey came only late, in the following year, and not all the members sent their data:

Out of 41 institutions only 28 sent the information requested. It has to be acknowledged that it was the peak time period of Covid, which made life very difficult for teaching staff. However, the 28 answers received show some substantial trends.

As can be seen in table 3 the predominant structures are 6 + 4 and 8 + 2 semesters, respectively, following the Bologna recommendations. However, a few programmes with a duration of 12 semesters were reported as well as a single programme of 4, 6 and 8 semesters.

Table 3: Programme Structure
(ENCoRE survey 2020/21, participation: 28 institutions out of 41)

Members	Bachelor (Semester)	Master (Semester)	Diploma (Semester)	Total (Semester)
2		4		4
1		6		6
1	6	2		8
2	8	3		11
5	8	2		10
9	6	4		10
1		10		10
3			10	10
2	8	4		12
2			12	12

Another important question in the survey was targeted at the number of the yearly admission of students. This is an important issue because it is the first hint concerning the number of emerging conservator-restorers per year, assuming that there are only a few dropouts. The numbers are as expected not homogeneous, but the average of 29 admitted candidates for bachelor studies or 5 and 6, respectively, year curricula gives a good idea about the situation.

Entrance exams are obligatory in 24 institutions; 4 institutions have other regulations for the access to study programmes and are not entitled to run entrance exams. (Table 4)

As the average admission of Master students amounts to 15 per institution it can be deduced that not all students continue after the Bachelor degree but exit their education and training at that point.

Table 4: Average Yearly Student Intake; Obligatory Entrance Exams
(ENCoRE survey 2020/21, participation: 28 institutions out of 41)

Degree	Number of Students
Bachelor / 1-Cycle Programmes	29
Master Programmes	15
Obligatory Entrance Exams:	24 members

Since the turn of the century PhD studies have formed an important part of education and training. They are offered by 15 institutions on an autonomous basis, whereas 4 institutions formally need another university. The average yearly admission of PhD students amounts to 4.4 per institution. (Table 5)

Table 5: PhD Studies
(ENCoRE survey 2020/21, participation: 28 institutions out of 41)

PhD Student Intake (Average)	4.4
15 Members	Award autonomous PhD
4 Members	PhD only in cooperation with other university

A central characteristic for conservation-restoration studies is the overall ratio theory / practice. The answers to this question in the survey show rather uniform data for Bachelor studies, mostly stating values between 40 and 60 % with a slight weight on practice. In contrast to this, the numbers given for the Master or 1-cycle programmes of 5 and 6 years differ much more. Although many programmes report values between 40 and 60 % there are answers specifying 20 or 80 % as extreme values for either theory and practice, with minimum/maximum numbers of 15 and 85 %. Given these large differences it seems impossible to name any reasonable average. (Table 6)

Table 6: Ratio Theory / Practice
(ENCoRE survey 2020/21, participation: 28 institutions out of 41)

	(Average %)	Min %	Max %
Theory (Bachelor)	45	20	60
Practice (Bachelor)	55	40	80
Theory (Master or 1-Cycle)	44	15	80
Practice (/Master or 1-Cycle)	56	20	85

In contrast to this, the answers to the question whether practice is performed on original objects or on dummies is quite homogeneous with an average of 82 % hands-on practice on original objects in the Bachelor studies and 98 % in the Master or 1-cycle curricula. Not a single programme is without predominant focus on original objects.

15 programmes include compulsory internships (5 missing answers), 17 programmes allow for internships as elective study components (6 missing answers) and in 3 programmes internships are not counted as part of the curriculum. (Table 7)

Table 7: Recognition of Internships
(ENCoRE survey 2020/21, participation: 28 institutions out of 41)

	Number of Institutions
Compulsory Internship	15 (5 n.a.)
Elective Internship	17 (6 n.a.)
No Internship:	3

Another critical aspect in a programme for conservation-restoration is the student:teacher ratio. The recommendation of ENCoRE's Document on Practice in Conservation-Restoration Education is 1:6 for practice; theory lectures normally don't have to be limited in numbers. The survey question was therefore related to the teaching of practice. Given the large differences of the size of the ENCoRE institutions, but maybe also due to one or the other misunderstanding when answering the question, the numbers given differ so much that no reliable average can be established. The value would be 10.6 students per teacher with a maximum of 25 and a minimum of 1 for Bachelor studies (19 answers) and 6.4 students per teacher with a maximum of 19 and a minimum of 1 for Master and 1-cycle curricula (26 answers). These numbers give not even a rough information. (Table 8)

Table 8: Ratio Theory / Practice
(ENCoRE survey 2020/21, participation: 28 institutions out of 41)

	Average	Min	Max	Answers
Student/Teacher Ratio Bachelor	10,6	1	25	19
Student/Teacher Ratio Master/1-Cycle	6,4	1	19	26

The problem encountered when asking for staff numbers yielded likewise no representative results. Despite the modified questions concerning staff numbers, no comparison between the human resources in the institutions can be drawn, as the employment conditions and obligations differ too much. In particular, part time teaching may be limited to very few hours or reach a considerable amount of time, and also fulltime staff may be limited in terms of teaching obligations. Another solution of getting an overview on the staff situations will have to be found. Only the answers concerning the gender distribution for students and staff gave solid numbers, as can be seen in Table 9.

Table 9: Gender Distribution
(ENCoRE survey 2020/21, participation: 28 institutions out of 41)

Groups	Percentage
male students	15%
female students	86%
male staff	36%
female staff	64%

Specialisations

Sparked by a discussion between Elis Marçal and the author, in 2018 the ENCoRE Board started discussions on the topic of specialization, with the aim to make the conservator-restorer education landscape more transparent, to enhance mobility and above all, to align education with the needs of the profession. For the ENCoRE board, the discussion was also targeted at having a better and more useful representation of its members on the website.

In a first step the board discussed how to deal with the naming of the specialisations, which seemed (and still seems) to be misleading, as they show different names for the same content. The names in Table 10 were taken from the websites of the members.

Table 10: Specialisations as they appear on the websites of the ENCoRE members

Easel painting, sculpture	Polychrome sculpture
Painting, polychrome sculpture	Siliceous objects
Painting, sculpture	Paper, books, photo, archival materials, film, digital materials
Panel painting, interior decoration	Paper, photo
Easel painting	Graphic documents
Painting	Paper, books, photo
Sculpture	Paper, books
Stone sculpture	Old books, prints
Stone sculpture, stone segments of architecture	Paper, leather
Wooden sculpture	Book, prints, antique leather
Wood, modern materials	Object
Mural painting, easel painting	Historic interiors
Mural painting	Stone
Mural painting, architectural surfaces	Stone, architecture decorations
Architecture and interior decoration	Stone, architecture elements
Mural painting, stone, stucco, architectural surfaces	Mural painting, stone
Paintings, contemporary art	Stone, ceramic
Paintings, sculpture, contemporary art	Metal
Contemporary art	Ceramics, glass, metals
Modern materials, media	Glass

The discussion focusing on this problem yielded two categories for distinguishing between specialisations: a material-based category and a function-based category. However, also this attempt proved to be problematic, as it turned out that in some instances using this differentiation a sharp distinction between some specialisations is neither possible nor useful. However, in the end a simplified list was developed, which is not based on a sharp differentiation but on the conventional, traditional labels. This list is certainly not yet the final product. Once the board has finalized it the result will be distributed to the members for potential amendments and for approval in the end.

The immediate use of this simplified categorization should nevertheless be the starting point for a more precise description of the programmes, to be presented on the ENCoRE website. A potential solution could be designing a table which shows the weight of the components constituting a specialization offered by a member in terms of a rough percentage. (Table 11).

Table 11: Potential description of specialisations offered

Designation of the specialisation field(s) offered	any material	natural history materials	architectural surface	books	ceramics	glass	leather	metals	mosaics	mural painting	new media / time-based media	painting (general)	easel painting	paper	parchment	photographs	polychrome sculpture	stained glass	stone, stonelike materials	synthetic polymers	textiles	wood	Total (%)
Paper				15			5							70	5						5		100
Painting/Sculpture													70				30						100
Object - Focus Wood		5											5				5					85	100
Mural Painting and Architectural Surface			15						5	80													100
Modern and Contemporary Art	40										30									30			100

The next logical topic of discussion aimed at characterizing the curriculum structure, in particular in respect to the specialization period. Another table was developed, based on ECTS, given the fact that each specialization needs teaching of theory as well as of practice, embedded in a structure containing also more general topics, as a fundament for all specializations. This table shows the study structure and the distribution of the essential components, so that in the end a comparison of programmes should be possible. It will be important when presenting the data on the website to keep the individual naming of the specialisations, but to introduce a system of making the information transparent for outsiders – for interested candidates, for those who plan student exchange etc. (Table 12). At the GA in Porto in 2022, 5 members agreed to test the table and then gave their comments and propositions for amendment.

Table 12. Potential description of study structure

Designation of the specialisation field(s) offered	BACHELOR								MASTER								DIPLOMA COURSE							
	ECTS general subjects	ECTS general hands-on practice	ECTS specialisation subjects	ECTS specialized hands-on	ECTS internship practice	ECTS electives	ECTS Bachelor thesis	Total ECTS Bachelor	ECTS general subjects	ECTS general hands-on practice	ECTS specialisation subjects	ECTS specialized hands-on	ECTS internship practice	ECTS electives	ECTS Master thesis	Total ECTS Master	ECTS general subjects	ECTS general hands-on practice	ECTS specialisation subjects	ECTS specialized hands-on	ECTS internship practice	ECTS electives	ECTS Diploma thesis	Total ECTS Diploma course
specialisation A	40	15	80	23	0	10	12	180	9	0	18	58	15	0	20	120								
specialisation B	33	10	75	35	8	4	15	180																
specialisation C																	45	20	43	122	30	10	30	300
specialisation D																	37	22	55	130	10	16	30	300

The board of ENCoRE is still working on the improvement of the website, which got a complete relaunch in 2023. In a next step, the presentation of the members and their programmes on it will be

improved, eventually using the tables described above, in order to show the educational offers in a way which is easy to understand.

My final question is: What is a Bachelor in CR? And what is a Bachelor supposed to be able to do? When Bachelors are so different from school to school, how can you change the university for Master studies? This approach is the next step in an effort to come to a coherent landscape of conservation-restoration education programmes, where bachelor graduates are comparable and their qualification can be recognized, for example in case of change of university. Coming to recognized definitions of the working fields of the final graduates is an aim probably equally far away, but we definitely have to work into this direction.

Material Science for Conservators Bridging the Gap Between Science and Conservation-Restoration Practice

Nanna Bjerregaard, Julie Nogel Jæger and Cecil Krarup Andersen*

School of Conservation (Copenhagen, Denmark)

* Contact Author: cka@kglakademi.dk

A challenge for conservation programs teaching both science and practice is that the students find it difficult to apply science concepts to the practical world of conservation. The Royal Danish Academy, Architecture, Design and Conservation we have tried to solve this challenge by introducing a material science course specially designed for conservators and taught by both chemist and conservators. The course is designed for all specialities within conservation and aims for a common understanding of materials and their properties. It is inspired by engineering programs but an extra practical element for conservators is added focusing mainly on cleaning and the use of adhesives as these are common elements in all specialisations within conservation. The course was developed over the last five years which has led to the present structure. Challenges and positive outcomes are discussed.

Introduction

One of the enduring challenges in conservation-restoration education is bridging the gap between scientific theory and hands-on practice. Students often struggle to apply the chemistry and physics they learn in the classroom to real-world conservation-restoration scenarios [1]. At the Royal Danish Academy - Architecture, Design and Conservation- in Copenhagen, one of the ways we have addressed this issue is by introducing a dedicated course in material science tailored to students of conservation-restoration.

In all conservation-restoration specialisations, science and practice are deeply intertwined. Valid conservation work cannot be performed without a solid understanding of the chemical and physical properties of materials used in the conservation-restoration work. Material science therefore serves as the crucial link between theory and practice, as well as between specialities offering a framework that combines structure, characterization, properties, processing, and performance of materials.

A Cross-Disciplinary Approach

Inspired by the fundamental material science courses commonly taught in engineering programs [2], our course aims to equip students with a comprehensive understanding of materials from a scientific perspective. However, we do not focus on material performance calculations important to

engineering but on the ability of the student to be able to explain and use material science terminology and theory to develop solutions for conservation-restoration problems. The course is an integral part of the second semester in the bachelor's program, serving as a unifying element despite the varied specializations students may pursue. At the Royal Danish Academy these specializations include BA programs in natural history, archival material, paintings and objects conservation (descriptions can be found on the institution's website). The material science course follows the introductory chemistry course completed in the first semester. It ensures direct use of and continues building on the achieved learning outcome. During the second semester Students will also be taught a fundamental preventive conservation course, which ensures a well-rounded educational foundation linking science, materials, and degradation agents.

To make this intended approach meaningful, we encourage students to shift their perspective, so rather than categorising objects by type (e.g., paper, textiles, bones, paintings), they are taught to view the objects through the lens of material composition such as polymers, ceramics, metals, composites, and biomaterials. This material-based classification fosters a deeper understanding of how materials behave and degrade.

Understanding Material Properties

A fundamental pillar of materials science is the comprehensive understanding of material properties. These properties include mechanical, thermal, electrical, magnetic, optical, and chemical characteristics. They are important for determining and recognizing how a material behaves under various conditions and ultimately dictating its suitability for specific applications or treatments. This understanding is essential for preparing objects for exhibitions, transport, storage or research purposes. Understanding material properties enables conservators to select the most appropriate material for a given application or treatment and helps predict how a material will respond to external forces, temperature changes or environmental exposure.

Knowledge of material properties also plays a key role in green and sustainable conservation [3]. By understanding how materials degrade or can be recycled, conservators can choose and use more environmentally friendly products and processes, reducing waste and material resources [4].

By applying scientific methods to study the physical and chemical properties of materials, it is possible to uncover the underlying causes of degradation and ensure that the integrity and longevity of precious items are maintained for future generations. The material science course also helps conservation students with a scientific language scaffold [5] which ensures a deeper understanding of what is taught and effective communication with scientists.

This scientific insight is crucial for making informed, evidence-based decisions in conservation. By analysing the chemical and physical properties of materials, conservators can better predict how objects will respond to various conservation treatments [6]. This knowledge is especially important when selecting the most effective preservation techniques for each object, particularly under the guiding principle of minimal, reversible, or retreatable interventions [7,8] Scientifically informed decisions ensure that conservation actions are not only respectful of the original materials but also adaptable to future advancements. By relying on evidence-based methods, conservations uphold

ethical standards, while maintaining the flexibility to revisit and refine treatments as new technologies and insights emerge.

Advanced materials, such as nanomaterials, consolidants, and protective coatings, are being developed to enhance conservation efforts. These innovations rely on a deep understanding of material behaviour to ensure they are effective, non-invasive, and environmentally safe. Scientific understanding provides the foundation for anticipating material behaviour and interactions, thereby empowering conservators to make responsible and resilient choices.

Course Structure and Content

The course is divided into two main components; The first part of the course focuses on developing a solid understanding of material properties by bridging chemical bonding, functional groups, and structures to physical and mechanical behaviour, and material characteristics. Through a combination of theoretical lessons and hands-on exercises—such as stress-strain analysis and FT-IR spectroscopy, the students gain practical skills in identifying material types and understanding their behaviour (Figure 1). The section also includes a thematic focus on fibres and an excursion to a material testing laboratory, offering insights into how scientific analysis supports conservation decision-making.

Figure 1: Outline of the key topics covered in the first part of the course, titled "Material Properties."

The second part of the course builds on translating theoretical knowledge into hands-on skills essential for conservation practice (figure 2). Students engage in a series of guided exercises involving adhesives and cleaning techniques, each designed to reinforce scientific principles through realistic conservation-restoration scenarios. These activities not only build technical proficiency but also encourage critical thinking about material compatibility, retreatability and ethical decision-making in conservation treatments.

Figure 2: Practical exercises covered in the second part of the course titled "Practical application"

Material Properties

At the outset of the course, students are asked to consider material identification, grouping of materials and central materials properties based on hand-on material examples (Figure 3). This exercise raises awareness of the importance of material science but also on the material science knowledge they already have from pure life experience. This introductory exercise gives rise to many very interesting class discussions on identification, terminology, and performance.

Students then progress to examining key physical properties of materials, such as strength, flexibility, brittleness, and density. They learn not only how to define and measure these properties, but also how to use them to compare and evaluate different materials. Emphasis is placed on interpreting what these characteristics mean in practical, real-world contexts, for example, why flexibility is crucial in wearable technologies, or why high strength and low density are desirable in aerospace components.

Throughout the course, students explore a wide range of material categories, including both naturally occurring and engineered materials. These include natural and synthetic polymers, oils and waxes, metals, ceramics, and composite materials. By investigating the unique properties and applications of each category in both theoretical lectures and practical exercises, students gain a comprehensive understanding of how materials are different and how they are selected and used across various industries and everyday products.

From this it is now time to delve into the fundamental building blocks of materials, beginning with an examination of their atomic structure. A central focus during this phase is understanding the various types of chemical bonds that govern how atoms are held together in different materials. These include covalent bonds, where atoms share electrons; ionic bonds, formed through the transfer of electrons between atoms; and metallic bonds, characterized by a 'sea' of delocalized electrons. The course also explores materials that exhibit a hybrid of these bonding types, highlighting how these interactions influence the material's overall properties and behaviour.

Understanding the nature of atomic bonds is fundamental to comprehending both the chemical and physical properties of materials. These bonds dictate how atoms are arranged in a structure, how they interact with one another, and how the material responds to external forces or environmental conditions. The type and strength of bonding influence key characteristics such as hardness, ductility, melting point, electrical conductivity, and thermal stability. For instance, strong covalent bonds can result in materials that are hard and brittle, like diamond, while metallic bonds contribute to the flexibility and conductivity of metals. This foundational knowledge is essential for analysing and predicting why certain materials are strong and durable, while others may be brittle or flexible, enabling more informed decisions in material selection and engineering applications.

Students are challenged with a fundamental question: Why is it important to understand the types of bonds present in materials? This question serves as a guiding thread throughout the course, encouraging students to think critically about the relationship between atomic interactions and material behaviour. By the end of the course, students are expected to confidently articulate how different bonding types directly influence a material's mechanical strength, electrical conductivity, thermal properties, and overall performance.

To deepen their understanding and encourage critical thinking, students are guided to ask and explore a series of essential questions throughout the course. These questions help them connect theoretical knowledge with practical insights and real-world applications. For example:

- What types of atomic bonds are present in this material, and how can we identify them?
- In what ways do these bonds influence the material's physical and chemical properties, such as strength, flexibility, or conductivity?
- Why might one material exhibit greater strength or flexibility than another, even if they appear similar?
- What fundamentally distinguishes a brittle material from one that is strong or ductile, and how can this be explained at the atomic level?

By engaging with these questions, students develop a habit of inquiry that goes beyond memorization. They learn to analyse materials from both microscopic and macroscopic perspectives, fostering a deeper appreciation for how atomic-scale interactions shape the performance and suitability of materials in various contexts.

This layered, bottom-up approach equips students with a comprehensive toolkit for analysing materials holistically. They learn to connect the dots between molecular structure and real-world performance, enabling them to assess materials not only in terms of their composition but also in terms of their functional roles in various contexts.

Moreover, students gain insight into how external factors, such as environmental conditions, mechanical stress, and conservation interventions, can alter or degrade materials over time. By understanding these interactions at both the micro and macro levels, students are better prepared to make informed decisions about material selection, preservation strategies, and restoration techniques.

Figure 3: One the very first course day students are asked to discuss material types, identification and properties based on material examples 1. Metals, 2. Ceramics, 3. Glass, 4. Elastomers, 5. Synthetic polymers, 6. Fiber reinforced composites, 7. Natural polymers (paper), 8. Natural polymers (textile), 9. Natural (bees-)wax, 10. Natural polymer (Leather), 11. Natural composite/polymer (wood), 12. Stone.

Applying Theory to Practice

The second part of the course serves as a crucial link between the theoretical foundations of the first part of the course and the practical implementation of material science in the field of conservation and restoration. After acquiring a solid understanding of the fundamental properties of materials, such as their structure, composition, and behaviour under various conditions, the students transition into exploring how these principles are applied in two practical scenarios: adhesion and cleaning; two practical cases in which predicting and controlling how different materials interact with one another are crucial in conservation-restoration.

Understanding adhesion helps students grasp how and why certain substances stick together, which is essential when selecting adhesives for repairs or when consolidating fragile surfaces. Meanwhile, studying both aqueous and organic cleaning systems provide insight into how materials dissolve or repel each other, which is knowledge that is crucial when choosing appropriate cleaning agents or when removing old restoration materials without damaging the original substrate.

By mastering these concepts, students are equipped to assess the compatibility of materials used in conservation treatments. This ensures that interventions are not only effective but also retreatable and safe for the long-term preservation of natural and cultural heritage. Through case studies, laboratory exercises, and critical analysis, students learn to make informed decisions that balance scientific understanding with ethical considerations in conservation practice.

This approach does also enhance their understanding of theoretical concepts and help them transfer scientific knowledge to real-life conservation challenges. These activities involve applying scientific

principles to practical tasks, such as testing the stability of materials, evaluating cleaning techniques or assessing the effect of environmental conditions on various substrates. Designed to bridge the gap between academic learning and professional practice (Andersen et al., 2018), these sessions provide students with valuable experience in navigating the complexities and decision-making processes that define conservation work.

By working with actual tools, materials, and mock-ups of heritage objects, students gain insight into the practical implications of their theoretical knowledge. They learn to observe, measure, and interpret results in context, developing a more intuitive and informed approach to conservation treatments. This experiential learning fosters confidence and competence, preparing students to navigate the complexities of real-world conservation with both scientific rigor and ethical sensitivity.

Assessment

The course concludes with an oral examination that serves as a comprehensive assessment of the students' knowledge, analytical skills, and communication abilities. Based on a poster produced by the students on a material of their own selection, students are required to:

- Compare and contrast different groups of materials, such as organic versus inorganic substances or natural versus synthetic polymers. This demonstrates their ability to recognize key characteristics, behaviours, and applications of various materials used in conservation.
- Explain the scientific principles underlying their observations, drawing on their understanding of material properties, chemical interactions, and physical behaviours. This includes articulating how factors like adhesion, solubility, aging, and environmental conditions influence conservation outcomes.

This oral examination is designed not only to test retention of knowledge, but also to assess the students' ability to synthesize complex information and communicate it clearly and confidently. These are essential competencies for professionals in conservation and heritage science, where interdisciplinary collaboration and public communication are often key to successful outcomes. The format encourages students to articulate their reasoning, defend their choices, and engage in critical discussion-skills that are vital for navigating the ethical and technical challenges of real-world conservation work.

Outcomes and Reflections

After delivering the course three times in 2020, 2022 and 2024, we have undertaken a continuous process of reflection and refinement to ensure that the curriculum remains responsive to student needs and aligned with the evolving landscape of conservation-restoration practice.

Student feedback has played a pivotal role in shaping the course's evolution, offering valuable insights into its effectiveness and impact. Many students report feeling significantly more confident and better prepared to make informed, scientifically grounded decisions in their conservation-restoration work. This growing confidence is not only a reflection of their improved technical proficiency but also

of their ability to think critically, evaluate options, and justify their choices using core principles of materials science.

As part of these ongoing improvements, we have made a significant structural change: the course has transitioned from a framework organized around distinct material groups (such as metals, ceramics, or polymers) to one centred on material properties. This shift reflects a more integrated and functional approach to understanding materials, emphasizing characteristics such as porosity, solubility, mechanical strength, and chemical reactivity, which are properties that directly influence conservation strategies and outcomes.

By focusing on how materials behave rather than simply categorizing them, students are better equipped to analyse and respond to the complex, interdisciplinary challenges they will encounter in professional practice. This property-based approach fosters a deeper, more transferable understanding of materials, enabling students to make informed decisions across a wide range of conservation contexts. These properties are then illustrated through examples drawn from various material groups, allowing students to understand how similar properties can manifest across different materials and contexts.

This change encourages a more analytical and transferable understanding of materials. It helps students develop the ability to compare and evaluate materials based on their behaviour and performance, rather than relying solely on classification. This approach also better supports interdisciplinary thinking and prepares students to make informed, property-based decisions in conservation-restoration work.

In addition, planning the material centred approach, we as teachers found it logical to start with chemical bonds and structures as a building block for physical and mechanical properties. However, by student feedback we discovered that introducing physical and mechanical properties and then explain the differences by material chemistry gave more meaningful and deeper learning. By this organisation of the themes the material science course was not just a prolongation of last semester's chemistry course but – for the students - a completely new angle to materials.

One of the most significant enhancements to the course has been the emphasis on practical techniques, particularly in the critical areas of cleaning and adhesion. By integrating hands-on training in these areas, the course enables students to translate theoretical knowledge into practical skills.

An especially meaningful outcome of the course has been the development of a shared vocabulary; a common language rooted in scientific terminology and conservation practice. This shared vocabulary enhances interdisciplinary communication, enabling students to collaborate more effectively with professionals across conservation, science, and heritage fields. It fosters mutual understanding and facilitates more cohesive, integrated approaches to complex conservation challenges.

The course has also served as a catalyst for greater collaboration among faculty members, encouraging alignment of teaching goals and reinforcing the central role of materials science as a unifying foundation within the broader conservation-restoration curriculum across specialisations.

This collaborative spirit has strengthened the coherence and consistency of the program, ensuring that students receive a well-rounded and interconnected educational experience.

Together, these developments reflect a shared commitment to excellence, among students, instructors, and the broader academic community, that continues to enrich the program and support the growth of a new generation of thoughtful, skilled, and scientifically literate conservation professionals.

Conclusion

By placing materials science at the heart of conservation-restoration education, the course aims to develop professionals who are not only skilled in practical techniques but also deeply rooted in scientific reasoning. This integrated approach equips students with the tools to approach conservation challenges with strategic insight, analytical clarity, and a collaborative mindset.

A thorough understanding of material properties enables students to anticipate how objects will respond to environmental changes, aging, and treatment interventions. This knowledge informs their decisions about appropriate conservation methods, enhances their ability to diagnose and deepens their comprehension of the chemical and physical principles that underpin conservation work.

Moreover, this scientific foundation plays a crucial role in interdisciplinary communication and across conservation specialisations. Students acquire a shared vocabulary that bridges the gap between conservators, scientists, and other heritage professionals. This common language fosters more effective collaboration, ensuring that conservation strategies are both scientifically sound and contextually appropriate.

Ultimately, the course prepares students not only to preserve cultural and natural heritage with care and precision, but also to be thoughtful, informed contributors to the broader conservation community. They emerge as professionals capable of navigating complex challenges, engaging in meaningful dialogue across disciplines, and advancing the field through evidence-based, ethically grounded practice.

References

1. Andersen, C. K., Federspiel, B. K., & Clemmensen, P. (2018). Bridging Conservation Practice and Science, A Study on Encapsulation Theory and Knowledge Transfer in the Education of Conservators. *Meddelelser Om Konservering*, 2018, 5–11.
2. Callister, W. D. (2007). *Materials science and engineering, an introduction* (7th Edition, 1–1). Wiley.
3. Balliana, E., Ricci, G., Pesce, C., & Zendri, E. (2016). Assessing the value of green conservation for cultural heritage: Positive and critical aspects of already available methodologies. *International Journal of Conservation Sciences*, 7, 185–202.
4. Di Turo, F., & Medeghini, L. (2021). How Green Possibilities Can Help in a Future Sustainable Conservation of Cultural Heritage in Europe. *Sustainability*, 13(7), 3609.
5. Wellington, J., & Osborne, J. (2001). *Language and Literacy in Science Education*. McGraw-Hill Education (UK).
6. Fuster-López, L., & Andersen, C. K. (2014). *Understanding structural conservation through materials science: Strategies and didactics* (W. Baatz, Ed.). CeROArt asbl.
7. Appelbaum, B. (1987). Criteria for treatment: Reversibility. *Journal of the American Institute for Conservation*, 2(26), 65–73.
8. Charteris, L. (1999). Reversibility – myth and misuse. In *Reversibility – Does it Exist?* (A. Oddy, ed.) pp. 141–145. London: British Museum.

Master's Degrees as a Tool for the Specialisation of the Conservation and Restoration Profession.

The Case of the *Escola Superior de Conservació i Restauració de Béns Culturals de Catalunya* (ESCRBCC)

M. Àngels Balliu Badia, Joan Escudé Gonzalez, Marta Pérez Azcárate*, Ruth Sadurní Codina
Escola Superior de Conservació i Restauració de Béns Culturals de Catalunya (Barcelona)

* Contact Author: mpere193@xtec.cat

At the Escola Superior de Conservació i Restauració de Béns Culturals de Catalunya, conservation and restoration studies began in 1992 with a three-year diploma that included four specialisations: archaeology, graphic documents, sculpture and painting. In 2010, with the implementation of the Bologna Plan, these studies were transformed into four-year degree courses. However, the high demand for supplementary training highlighted the desire of conservators and restorers to pursue advanced expertise and the need for specialised professionals in the workplace.

To deal with this demand, the school has developed two master's degree options: the Master's Degree in Artistic Education in the Conservation and Restoration of Photographic Heritage and the Master's Degree in Artistic Education in the Preventive Conservation of Movable and Immovable Cultural Heritage.

In this paper we present the criteria applied for the choice of these two specializations, the process of verifying the qualifications and the tools to evaluate their impact on our professional environment within our territorial scope.

Introduction

Catalonia has an exceptionally rich, extensive, and diverse cultural heritage, which constitutes not only a legacy to be preserved, but also a point of connection with the past and a key resource for collective identity, capable of contributing to true progress. The fundamental laws in our country establish the duty to preserve this heritage, a task that requires professionals equipped with sound judgment and technical knowledge to ensure the fulfilment of this mandate.

It is within this context that the need arose in Catalonia to train qualified, competitive professionals capable of carrying out complex conservation and restoration (CR) interventions with the highest standards of quality, supported by a comprehensive, interdisciplinary, and specialized education.

Since its foundation, the *Escola Superior de Conservació i Restauració de Béns Culturals de Catalunya*¹ (ESCRBCC) in Barcelona has evolved to adapt to professional and academic needs, offering public and specialised training in the CR of cultural heritage. From the very beginning, our point of view has been that specialization is indeed the key to address the intrinsic complexity of cultural heritage objects and to acquire the deep material knowledge needed for its conservation. Although CR cannot be understood in a fragmented manner, these studies necessarily require a degree of specialization. Accordingly, the degree is structured around various areas of specialization, typically organized first by object type and subsequently by the constituent materials of the cultural heritage. The specializations developed in this first curriculum were:

- Archaeology (ceramics, glass, metals, bone, etc.)
- Graphic documents (paper, cardboard, parchment, leather, etc.)
- Painting (canvas, wood, murals, etc.)
- Sculpture (metal, wood, stone, terracotta, etc.)
- Textiles (not implemented)

Based on these purposes, the specializations in Conservation and Restoration respond to the need to provide comprehensive training that encompasses technical and instrumental skills, theoretical knowledge, and technological competencies. This approach provides a holistic and generalist educational framework, viewing education as an evolving process of personal development.

In this context, the training is designed not only to provide specialized expertise, but also to foster broad practical principles that enable individuals to develop critical thinking and autonomy. Ultimately, the goal is to prepare professionals who can adapt to and integrate within today's diverse socio-cultural environments, both locally and internationally.

The Initial Curriculum Design and the Development of Facilities

The CR studies offered by the ESCRBCC are part of the so-called Higher Artistic Studies (EAS for its denomination in Catalan and Spanish), an official Spanish system equivalent to University Degrees for artistic studies outside the university space. Besides CR, these are studies within the fields of music, dancing, drama arts, design and plastic arts. Recently, with the implementation of a new specific law in 2024, also other disciplines have been added: visual arts and cinema, circus arts and creative writing. Some of them can be found also in the University system, but usually without any specialisation.

These EAS are at the same educational level as University Degrees and can be taken also from upper secondary education or from higher vocational education, known in Spain as *Formación Profesional* (Professional training).

¹ Higher School of Conservation and Restoration of Cultural Heritage of Catalonia.

The first academic curriculum of the ESCRBC was established in 1992 and took the form of a three-year diploma program, consisting of a common first year followed by two years of specialization. Each academic year included a weekly schedule of 32 teaching hours, covering 8 to 10 subjects per year. The initial curriculum offered five specializations: painting, sculpture, archaeological materials, graphic documents, and textiles [1].

In 1993, renovation and expansion work began on the school's main building. One of the project's primary objectives was to ensure that each proposed specialization would have its own workshop. However, due to limitations in space, infrastructure, and resources, only four of the five originally proposed specializations have been offered to date: painting, sculpture, archaeological materials, and graphic documents. Each of these specializations is supported by two conservation ateliers, one for each year of specialization (the 2nd and 3rd years in the former diploma program, and the 3rd and 4th years in the current degree structure). These ateliers are equipped with specialized instruments and tools suited to the technical needs of each discipline.

The original academic program was phased out in the 2011-2012 academic year (Figure 1). Since its implementation, a total of 697 students graduated from the program.

Figure 1: ESCRBC timeline

Adaptation to the European Higher Education Area

In 2010, the ESCRBC began to implement a new curriculum, structured in four academic years corresponding to the Bachelor's degree in CR of Cultural Heritage (240 ECTS credits). This step forward is a response to the changes brought into the European Higher Education Area (EHEA), as a result of the so-called "Bologna Process", which began in 1999. This new plan was articulated in two common courses and two specialization courses, based on the Spanish legislation (Resolution

EDU/3777/2010; Royal Decree 635/2010). The plan was also approved by the Catalonia Education Department and the *Agency for the Quality of the University System of Catalonia* (AQUCatalunya)[2].

This was both a challenge and an opportunity to reassess the educational programme at ESCRBCC, to ensure the development of our students' professional skills at the highest level. At that time, there was an internal discussion about shifting to a specialisation structure based on materials, distinguishing between organic and inorganic materials. However, the Ministry of Education decided to keep the same specialities but adding another one: Furniture. Moreover, each category was subdivided by composition and typology, adapting the content to the degree. Nevertheless, we introduced the division between organic and inorganic materials in the common first two years of the degree (before the specialization) which aims to provide general knowledge of the materials composition.

The general, transversal and specific competencies for each specialization are aligned with the requirements established by the European Network for Conservation-Restoration Education (ENCoRE), by the European Confederation of Conservator-Restorers' Organizations (E.C.C.O.) [3], by the Spanish group of the International Institute of Conservation (GE-IIC) and by the International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property (ICCROM). The professional profiles corresponding to the four specialties that have been taught since the beginning of the ESCRBCC are the following:

- Specialist in CR of archaeological heritage: technician specially qualified for the CR of archaeological objects and their constituent materials.
- Specialist in CR of graphic documents: technician specially qualified for the CR of books, documents and graphic works, and their constituent materials.
- Specialist in sculpture CR: technician specially qualified for the CR of sculptural works of art and their constituent materials.
- Specialist in CR of painting: technician specially qualified for the CR of the pictorial works of art and their constituent materials.

In each case, the professional also develops expertise on the determination of the criteria and best strategies of intervention for each material, including the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities to define, decide and carry out treatments on the materials specific to their specialty, guaranteeing their integrity and permanence. So finally, the new degree with specialization was adapted to level 6 European Qualifications Framework (EQF) and has been verified in accordance with the successive reports issued by AQUCatalunya, an agency registered in the European Quality Assurance Register for Higher Education (EQAR).

The Introduction of the Masters

The changes brought by the new study plan did not lead, though, to any significant improvements in the space used to teach the courses or the equipment available at the school. This made it very difficult to introduce the remaining specialties (textile and furniture) and meant that new undergraduate specialties could not be set up.

However, there was still one other option left, the new ordinance gave the possibility to start the path of postgraduate studies. The recent data highlights the growing need for greater specialisation among professionals in the sector. According to the report "Study on the problems of the conservation-restoration sector in Catalonia", prepared by the *Associació Professional de Conservadors-Restauradors de Catalunya*²(CRAC), in 2019 only 17% of conservators-restorers had a specialised master's degree in conservation-restoration, while 87% had a degree or diploma. In contrast, 78% of professionals were actively seeking specialisation courses after completing their studies [4]. A key factor contributing to the lack of professionals with a Master's degree in Catalonia is the limited availability of Master's programmes in CR. In response to the growing demand for professional specialisation, the ESCRBCC has started to incorporate new specialisations in professional fields that demand the higher level of expertise that can be offered by a master's degree.

Following this idea, the ESCRBCC has developed two Masters' degrees: the Master in Artistic Education in the CR of Photographic Heritage (starting in the academic year 2019-2020) and the Master in Artistic Education in the Preventive Conservation of Movable and Immovable Property (starting in the academic year 2024-2025).

These master's degrees align with the Spanish 4+1 education system, which consists of four years of undergraduate studies followed by one year of master's-level education, in accordance with the European Higher Education Area (EHEA) framework. Government regulations are generally more complex for specialization programs than for master's degrees, making master's programs a more accessible and structured path for advanced training. With regard to school facilities, this structure allows master's classes to be scheduled in the afternoon, as bachelor's courses take place in the morning. This flexible scheduling also facilitates collaboration with external professionals from outside the public education system, enriching the program with highly specialized expertise. These master's programs are aligned with the objectives of the CHARTER project [5], as they contribute to the training of competent professionals in under-represented specialities. Furthermore, they adhere to the E.C.C.O. and ENCoRE guidelines on professional competences, ensuring that students complete the 300 ECTS credits required to meet the professional standards in the field of conservation.

In 2016, the school started working in the first Master's program and started teaching it in 2019. In the following sections we present the criteria used for the selection of these two specialisations, the process of verifying the qualifications and the tools used to evaluate their impact on the professional environment of the CR within our territorial scope.

Master's Degree in Art Education in the Conservation-Restoration of Photographic Heritage

Criteria, data and studies on the potential need for the degree and its interest for society. Background and previous experiences

² Professional Association of Conservators-Restorers of Catalonia.

In 2015, the ESCRBCC began a research and consultation process to determine which master's degree to teach, based on teaching experience, the detection of needs in the sector and consultation with external professionals and experts. After evaluating several options, it was decided to start working on the Master in Art Education in the CR of Photographic Heritage, thus responding to a training gap in this field in Catalonia.

Between 2003 and 2013, the ESCRBCC organized five monographic courses on photographic conservation, open to both students and professionals, as previous experience and foundation for the master's degree. These courses demonstrated the interest and need for specific training in this field, reinforcing the idea of offering a specialized master's degree.

However, there are data and studies on the potential demand for the degree and its interest for society since 1996, when the Department of Culture of the Generalitat of Catalonia drafted the *White book on photographic heritage in Catalonia* [6]. This paper was created with the purpose of establishing the state of the matter, both with regard to photography found in image archives and public and private photographic funds, and with regard to author photography. The results showed that in Catalonia there was no regulated training in photography CR beyond that of the courses that were organized from time to time and related conferences.

In 2015, the Department of Culture also presented the *National Photography Plan* [7] the tool that established the instruments for protection, preservation and description of Catalan photographic heritage, and that also detected the absence of photography conservation in CR training programs.

With the aim of defining the skills of conservators-restorers specialized in photography, a commission of experts was created to propose the creation of a specific university master's degree. The ESCRBCC took on this initiative and began to work on its structuring. At the state level, the *National Plan for the Conservation of Photographic Heritage* [8] of 2015, promoted by the Institute of Cultural Heritage of Spain (IPCE), based in Madrid, pointed out the lack of regulated higher education in this field, despite the existence of courses and postgraduate courses aimed at archivists and photographers. Both studies considered, in addition, that including the CR of photographs in the study plan of the specializations in the CR of graphic documents, indicated that the conservation of graphic documents was still confused with the specialization in photography conservation, and showed the lack of social understanding about the reality of photographic heritage.

The conclusion of all these data and studies was obvious: there was a lack of an official and specific training offer at the level of higher studies (degree or master's degree or equivalent qualification) in the CR of photographic heritage in Catalonia and Spain. The potential demand for the title and its interest for Catalan and Spanish society was high, as shown by the two national photography plans.

Relation of the proposal with the socio-economic characteristics of the area of influence of the degree that justifies the need and demand for specialized professionals

According to data from the *National Photography Plan* (2015), Catalonia has more than 35 million inventoried photographs, a number that is constantly growing. However, the number of

conservators-restorers specialized in photography is very small, with many professionals trained in graphic document but without regular training in photography conservation.

In addition, the low visibility of this heritage and the lack of specialized resources motivated the creation of the portal *Photography in Catalonia* (2015), the first online space dedicated to the dissemination of Catalan photographic heritage. This growing interest in photographic conservation was also reflected in the increase of online resources – especially from North American institutions – and international educational initiatives, evidencing a global need for regulated training in this field.

External referents that endorsed the adequacy of the proposal to national and international criteria for degrees with similar academic characteristics.

The field of photography conservation began to develop in the 1970s in the *International Museum of Photography and Film* at the *George Eastman House* of Rochester (New York). The development of photographic conservation as an academic discipline has been uneven internationally. In the US and Canada, universities such as Rochester, Delaware and Ryerson have developed specific programs. In Europe, some institutions have incorporated this training into broader master's degrees, such as the Hochschule für Technik und Wirtschaft of Berlin and the Staatlichen Akademie der Bildenden Künste of Stuttgart (Germany), the Instituto Politécnico of Tomar (Portugal) or the Haute École des Arts of Bern (Switzerland) [9].

In Spain, photographic conservation subjects are found in master's degrees aimed at photographers and archivists, but not in programs specifically aimed at conservators-restorers. This makes the ESCRBCC master's degree unique, as it focuses exclusively on photographic CR, covering both preventive and curative conservation.

It should also be emphasized that the ESCRBCC master's degree proposal meets the international criteria promoted by the associations E.C.C.O and ENCoRE and assumed in Catalonia for CRAC. It should be remembered that these associations promote that only those who have a specific training of five years in CR can exercise the profession of conservator-restorer. The ESCRBCC master's proposal can put an end to the educational confusion that the *National Plan for the Conservation of Photographic Heritage*, to professional intrusiveness and well-intentioned voluntarism that often acts with little scientific knowledge.

Internal and external consultations for the preparation of the study plan.

For the preparation of the study plan, several internal and external consultations were carried out, which made it possible to count on the opinion and advice of the ESCRBCC faculty, as well as professionals and institutions in the sector, which demonstrate a broad consensus in the preparation of the proposal in the teaching and professional field. The whole process went from 2014 to 2024 (Figure 2).

In 2015, the ESCRBCC presented the Master's proposal to the Department of Education of the Generalitat de Catalunya for approval. Various consultations were held with professionals and institutions in the sector, and work was being done on the drafting of the *Title Verification Report*

(MVT), following the guidelines established by AOU Catalunya³ according to the standards and criteria for the evaluation of university degrees and masters in accordance with the *European Standards and Guidelines* (ESG) of 2015, whose main objective is to guarantee the equivalence between the training received and the European qualification level. The verification was confirmed on June 5, 2017, and accreditation on April 26, 2024⁴ (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Master in CR of photographic Heritage: consultations for the preparation of the study plan, verification and accreditation.

Finally, the master's degree was approved and began to be taught in the 2019-2020 academic year. Since its launch, it has had four editions, with a total of 42 students enrolled. The fifth edition is scheduled for the 2025-2026 academic year.

Establishing objectives

The Master's Degree in Art Education in the CR of Photographic Heritage aims to train professionals specialized in photography CR, responding to the lack of training programs in this field in Catalonia and Spain.

This master's degree, of a professional nature, offers advanced, methodological and scientific training, addressing the characterization of materials, degradation processes and treatments applicable to photographic heritage. In addition, it includes internships in institutions that preserve photographic collections, providing real experience to students and facilitating their insertion into the labour market.

The program also allows graduates to develop skills for strategic planning, diagnosis and preparation of conservation-restoration plans, ensuring the long-term preservation of photographic heritage. Finally, it opts for diffusion of the results of the studies, through the publication of the best qualified Final Master's Project in the school's digital repository⁵ and *UNICUM* journal, a publication specialized in conservation-restoration published by the ESCRBC⁶.

³ See: <https://estudis.aqu.cat/informes/Web/Titulacio/Detail?titulacioid=14449&idioma=ca-ES&titulacioid=14449&idioma=ca-ES>

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ See: <https://www.esrbcc.cat/en/final-project-digital-repository/>

⁶ See: <https://unicum.esrbcc.cat/index.php/unicum>

Master's Degree in Artistic Education in Preventive Conservation of Movable and Immovable Cultural Heritage

Criteria, data and studies on the potential need for the degree and its interest for society. Background and previous experiences

In 2019, with the desire to carry on giving continuity to undergraduate studies, the ESCRBCC started the arrangements to incorporate a second master's degree. This was probably the time to focus on preventive conservation, as, despite being a consolidated discipline in some European countries, especially in the United Kingdom, was still in an initial phase in Catalonia.

Adapting to the Bologna process, the ESCRBCC considered it essential to include preventive conservation as its own subject of 6 ECTS credits in the second year of the Bachelor's degree, understanding it as a transversal subject. Likewise, it was decided to integrate it into different subjects of CR of the four specialties taught.

A specific preventive conservation position was also created at the Centre de Restauració de Béns Mobles de Catalunya⁷(CRBMC), which opened the way to new job opportunities in public and private institutions. And in 2019 a course on *Preventive Conservation Plan for Museum Equipment* was organized with the support of the IPCE in the National Art Museum of Catalonia (MNAC), the biggest art museum in the country, which integrated this specialty into its future strategy, including the drafting of a preventive conservation plan.

On the other hand, the CRAC association worked to achieve the regulatory recognition of preventive conservation as a specific function of the conservator-restorer.

With national and international external references, it was observed that preventive conservation was a relatively modern discipline within the field of cultural heritage preservation.

Although the first publications and courses on preventive conservation date from the 1980s, the first key European document is the *Vantaa resolution* (2000), promoted by ICCROM and the European Commission [10]. This resolution established that all professionals who work with collections must have adequate training in this field.

In 2003, the *International Institute for Conservation of Historic and Artistic Works* (IIC) defined preventive conservation as an essential function of conservators-restorers. The same year, E.C.C.O. incorporated preventive conservation and adhered it to its ethical codes, prioritizing it over any other intervention. In 2004, the ICOM-CC recognized it as a fundamental element in the policies of museums and collections [11]

From here, relevant rules and standards were developed according to the consultation of the European Commission with UNESCO, ICCROM, ICOM and Europa nostra among others, to reach a

⁷ Movable Heritage Restoration Center of Catalonia.

consensus on the fundamental principles of quality applicable to interventions in the cultural heritage. The resulting document guided the Technical Committee 346 (CEN/TC 346) of the European Committee for Standardization (CEN), the body responsible for establishing rules and standards at European level, which published the first rule referring to preventive conservation in 2012 [12], and its review in 2018.

The evolution of the discipline was evident in the second Preventive Conservation Congress in Turin in 2018, where it was noted that some countries have achieved a high degree of specialization with approaches towards sustainability.

At the state level, in the regulatory aspect, the Law 16/1985 on Spanish Historical Heritage and the Royal Decree of 1986 had not yet incorporated preventive conservation as a fundamental principle. However, some regional regulations partially refer to it. It is not developed in Law 3/1993 of Catalan Cultural Heritage, but it was briefly mentioned in the Regulations for the Protection of Archaeological and Paleontological Heritage [13].

In this context, the IPCE approved the *National Preventive Conservation Plan* in 2011, revised in 2015, establishing organizational models and management tools to guarantee the preservation of cultural heritage [14]. This plan, together with the later one *National Emergency Plan and Risk Management in Cultural Heritage* [15], is a sign that the institutional impulse is beginning to materialize.

In Catalonia, the *Plan of Museums* of 2017 provided for the creation of a system of reserves and collection centres, as well as a technical commission to evaluate the implementation of preventive conservation [16]. This line was reinforced in 2019 in the *Forum of Museums 2019*, where the definition of professional profiles was debated. Despite these advances, preventive conservation was still perceived as a fragmented task between different professionals, evidencing the need for specific training.

Relation of the proposal with the socio-economic characteristics of the area of influence of the degree in order to establish the need and demand for the master's degree

Several studies pointed to a high demand for preventive conservation specialists. CRAC association, in a report published in 2020, revealed that this specialty is the second most requested by professionals in the sector.

During the 2019-2020 academic year, a survey of 102 students and 93 *alumni* of the ESCRBCC showed a high interest in training in this field: 94.6% considered it necessary to offer a master's degree in preventive conservation, and 72% would enrol in it [9].

It was therefore considered that the potential demand for the degree by current students and *alumni* of the ESCRBCC was very high. In addition, given that there are no training offers at this level in the rest of Spain, and as it was planned as a blended training programme, it was also suitable for students from outside Catalonia.

External referents that endorsed the adequacy of the proposal to national and international criteria for degrees with similar academic characteristics

In Europe, some general preventive conservation master's degrees were being carried out, and it were mainly concentrated in the United Kingdom, with four proposals focused on this discipline and two that incorporated related content, together with the proposal of the Sorbonne in France and that of Iberomus which integrates the Ibero-American community [9].

Whereas in Spain, only short-term specialization courses, unofficial post-graduate degrees and some preventive conservation subjects in some master's degrees had been implemented.

The ESCRBCC considered that its proposal was unique, as it was based on a specific training in conservation-restoration, guaranteeing a rigorous specialization aligned with the criteria set by the Ministry of Education. And above all, because of its admission requirement. The ESCRBCC considers that only graduates of a specific training in conservation-restoration are the ideal profile to enrol in the specialization in preventive conservation offered by this master's degree.

Curriculum development and approval

In 2019, the Master's Committee was created at the ESCRBCC, which prepared the initial proposal with the advice of national and international experts. At the beginning of 2020, it was submitted to the Department of Education of the Generalitat of Catalunya for approval.

Several meetings were held with representatives of the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB), formalizing a collaboration agreement for internships and research. In October 2021, the proposal was approved by the ESCRBCC and submitted to AQU Catalunya for verification, according to the standards and criteria for the evaluation of university degrees and masters in accordance with the *European Standards and Guidelines (ESG)* of 2015, whose main objective is to guarantee the equivalence between the training received and the European qualification level. The verification was confirmed July 8, 2022. The whole process took almost four years (Figure 3).⁸

Figure 3: Master in CR preventive conservation: consultation, curriculum development and verification.

⁸ See: <https://estudis.aqu.cat/informes/Web/Titulacio/Detail?titulacioid=15597>

Establishing objectives

The Master's Degree in Art Education in the Preventive Conservation of Movable and Immovable Cultural Heritage aims to train professionals specialized in this emerging discipline within conservation-restoration. Its application goes beyond museums and collections, including the preservation of movable heritage attached to buildings and archaeological sites [17].

This master's degree is a pioneer in the European Higher Education Area, as it addresses both movable and immovable property. In addition to the professional approach, it offers an introduction to research, opening the door to future doctoral theses in collaboration with UAB doctoral programs.

Thus, this qualification responds to a growing need for training in preventive conservation, both at regional, national and international level, consolidating itself as a unique opportunity for the professionalization of the sector.

As in the previous master's degree, the results of the studies are disseminated through the publication of the best qualified Final Master's Project in the school's digital repository⁹ and in the UNICUM journal¹⁰.

Accreditation and Quality Assurance

The courses taught by the ESCRBCC go through the evaluation, verification, accreditation and quality certification process certified by AQU Catalunya. AQU Catalunya is an independent agency that, since its creation in 1996, has as its objective the evaluation, accreditation and certification of quality in the field of universities and EAS centres in Catalonia. AQU Catalunya has been involved in the process of verification and accreditation of EAS degrees in Catalonia since 2012.

AQU Catalunya is a founding and full member of the European Association for Quality Assurance in Higher Education (ENQA) and was one of the first three agencies to be included in EQAR. The first essential requirement to start any verification and accreditation process is that the centre has an Internal Quality Guarantee System (SGIQ). The SGIQ is the system that establishes the procedures that define the centre's quality policy regarding training programs, academic planning, teaching and assessment methodology, student admission, enrolment and guidance, mobility, job placement, external internships, personnel policies, the management of resources and services of the centre, improvement proposals and the public provision of all information. This system was also evaluated and audited by AQU Catalunya and validated in 2015¹¹. Once the SGIQ was established, the verification report for the new degree could start [18]. This report is sent to AQU Catalunya, evaluated and monitored the following years with subsequent yearly reports. During the first 4 years, the centre draws up an annual Degree Monitoring Report (IST) which is assessed by AQU Catalunya. Once the accreditation process is passed, the ISTs become biannual. Every 4 years, master's degrees go through an accreditation process, which is the verification that the degree is being developed as planned in

⁹ See: <https://www.esrbcc.cat/en/final-project-digital-repository/>

¹⁰ See: <https://unicum.esrbcc.cat/index.php/unicum>

¹¹ See: https://www.esrbcc.cat/escola/qualitat/#garantia_qualitat

the verification. In this process the centre must submit a self-report and also receive a visit from an External Evaluation Committee that will issue an external evaluation report (Figure 4).

Figure 4: ESCRBCC courses: verification, accreditation and quality certification process.

Based on the external visit report of the centre where the degree to be accredited is awarded, the specific evaluation committee for the degree field — Arts and Humanities in our case — issues the degree accreditation report which can be favourable or unfavourable and which is structured in four levels: accredited with excellence, accredited, accredited with conditions and not accredited.

Results

To sum up, we will show some results of the Master's in artistic studies of CR of Photographic Heritage. The results of the Master's in Preventive Conservation are not yet available, as this course is being taught in its first edition (Figure 5). The graph on the left shows a progressive decrease in the number of enrolled students, which is why the possibility of teaching it every two years, instead of annually, is being considered. On the other hand, the graph on the right shows the degree of student satisfaction according to the data taken from a series of surveys carried out during the last three editions, with very positive results.

Figure 5: Master programs: results

The 2019 job match rate results show a high level of student satisfaction (74.2%), reflecting the success of the program in preparing graduates for the job market.

These data highlight the importance of continuous training as a fundamental tool for successful job placement and for the exercise of quality professional practice in a sector that requires increasingly specialized knowledge.

Conclusions

The development of these master's degrees represents a significant advance in conservation-restoration training in Catalonia. They fulfil the guidelines of E.C.C.O. and ENCoRE, allowing CR graduates to complete their specific five-year training, aligning with the 4+1 model established for the Spanish university system.

In addition, these programs contribute to cover training needs and are born from demands and necessities from the professional field in the heritage sector. As promoted by the CHARTER project, they facilitate professionalization in growing fields, as well as in research in the case of preventive conservation. They also have been proved as a quicker academic option in order to create degrees capable of reacting to new challenges and requirements in response to the needs of the society.

The practical and specialized orientation of the programs ensure that graduates are prepared to face the challenges of photographic CR and the preventive conservation of movable and immovable property, consolidating themselves as reference academic options at national and international level.

Acknowledgements

The authors want to thank Ph.D. Prof. Montgarri Castillo, who generously reviewed the English version of this manuscript.

References

1. Figueras, Xavier & Mirambell, Miquel. (2012). Vint anys formant conservadors-restauradors de béns culturals. *Unicum*, 11. <https://raco.cat/index.php/UNICUM/article/view/282787>
2. Mirambell, Miquel. (2010). El nou Grau de conservació i restauració de béns culturals. Un repte per a l'ESCRBCC. *Unicum*, 9. <https://raco.cat/index.php/UNICUM/article/view/287944>
3. E.C.C.O. (2002, 2003). *Professional Guidelines (I, II, III)*. https://www.ecco-eu.org/home/ecco-documents/#__ECCO_Professional_Guidelines__
4. Loran, Margarida. (2020). *Estudi sobre l'estat actual del sector de la conservació-restauració a Catalunya 2019. Memòria del projecte i resultats obtinguts*. CRAC, DGPC.
5. CHARTER, the European Cultural Heritage Skills Alliance. (2025). <https://charter-alliance.eu/>
6. Rigol, Josep (coord.). (1996). *Llibre blanc del patrimoni fotogràfic a Catalunya*. Generalitat de Catalunya. Departament de Cultura. <https://drac.cultura.gencat.cat/handle/20.500.12368/429#page=3>
7. Generalitat de Catalunya. Departament de Cultura. (n.d.). *Pla Nacional de Fotografia*. <https://drac.cultura.gencat.cat/handle/20.500.12368/32285#page=15>
8. Ministerio de Educación, Cultura y Deporte. (2015). *Plan Nacional de Conservación del Patrimonio Fotográfico*. Ministerio de Educación, Cultura y Deporte. <https://www.cultura.gob.es/planes-nacionales/dam/jcr:e97e9f56-5c1c-4192-96bf-3c02fbd6cad3/11-maquetado-patrimonio-fotografico.pdf>
9. Escola Superior de Conservació i Restauració de Béns Culturals de Catalunya. (2023). *Memòria per a la verificació del títol oficial del màster en ensenyaments artístics en conservació de patrimoni fotogràfic*. ESCRBCC. https://www.escribcc.cat/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/08044961_ESCRBCC_verifica_master_act_2023.pdf
10. ICCROM, EVTEK, Instituto Português de Conservação e Restauro, Centre de Recherche et de Restauration des Musées de France, i Ministry of Cultural Heritage of Hungary. (2000). *European Preventive Conservation Strategy. Vantaa*. European Commission.
11. Putt, N. & Slade, S. (2004). *Teamwork for preventive conservation*. ICCROM. www.iccrom.org/ifrcdn/pdf/ICCROM_01_Teamwork_en.pdf
12. Comité Europeo de Normalización (CEN). (2012). *CEN/TC 346 – Conservación del Patrimonio Cultural. Nueva estructura y avance normativo*. European Committee for Standardization.
13. Generalitat de Catalunya. (2002). *Decret 78/2002, de 5 de març, del Reglament de protecció del patrimoni arqueològic i paleontològic*. Diari Oficial de la Generalitat de Catalunya (DOGC) núm. 3591.
14. Carrión, A. (coord.). (2015). *Plan Nacional de Conservación Preventiva*. Ministerio de Educación, Cultura y Deporte.
15. Subdirección General del Instituto del Patrimonio Cultural de España. (2015). *Plan Nacional de Emergencias y Gestión de Riesgos en Patrimonio Cultural*. Ministerio de Educación, Cultura y Deporte. <https://sede.educacion.gob.es/publiventa/plan-nacional-de-emergencias-y-gestion-de-riesgos-en-patrimonio-cultural/patrimonio-historico-artistico/20705C>
16. Generalitat de Catalunya, Departament de Cultura. (2018). *Museus 2030. Pla de museus de Catalunya*. Generalitat de Catalunya. https://cultura.gencat.cat/web/.content/sscc/pla-museus-2030/documents/PMC_web.pdf
17. Escola Superior de Conservació i Restauració de Béns Culturals de Catalunya. (2022). *Memòria per a la verificació del títol oficial del màster en ensenyaments artístics en conservació preventiva de béns culturals mobles i immobles*. https://www.escribcc.cat/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/MVT-Conservacio-Preventiva-catala.rev2_.pdf
18. Agència per a la Qualitat del Sistema Universitari de Catalunya (AQU Catalunya). (2022). *Guia per a l'elaboració, la verificació i la modificació de titulacions universitàries de grau i màster*. AQU Catalunya. <https://www.aqu.cat/ca/Estudis/Difusio/Publicacions/Cercador-de-publicacions/Guia-per-a-l-elaboracio-verificacio-i-modificacio-de-titulacions-universitaries-de-grau-i-masters-2022>

Toward an Enhanced Definition of the Specialisation Areas for Portuguese Conservators-Restorers

David Teves Reis, Luís Pereira, Elis Marçal

ARP – Associação Profissional de Conservadores-restauradores de Portugal; Portugal

* Contact Author: davidtevesreis@gmail.com

Abstract

In 2019, the Board of ARP (Associação Profissional de Conservadores-restauradores de Portugal) reviewed and amended its Statutes and Internal Regulations, which were approved in February 2020. A key discussion point was the assessment of existing specialisations of the conservator-restorer, and the proposal of new ones. These are essential criteria for membership in the professional association. In 2024, with the revision of the Decree-Law governing interventions on protected heritage, the definition of specialisations became crucial as they impact the law's implementation.

Founded in 1995, ARP initially recognised only thirteen specialisations. However, the existing range was inadequate for evolving professional needs. As the understanding of cultural heritage expanded and the technical and scientific fields within conservation-restoration advanced, it became clear that a revision of specialisations was necessary.

The review process began with an evaluation of how cultural heritage is identified in Portugal, the criteria for defining specialisations, and how other European Confederation of Conservator-Restorers' Organisations (E.C.C.O.) member associations and international bodies organise their specialisations. The goal was to balance Portuguese heritage preservation needs with national regulations, while addressing professional recognition and mobility for members. This ongoing process requires continuous evaluation to foster innovation in cultural heritage conservation.

Framing the Professional Practice of Conservator-Restorers: Specialising or Generalising Models?

Different frameworks and national legislative systems coexist in conservation-restoration practice as in delineating the appropriate professional profiles, varying in the definition, identification, recognition, and characterisation of conservators-restorers and their activities globally. Despite international alignments and convergences, shaped by principles and guidelines of soft laws, current approaches continue to follow national needs and contexts.

There are multiple views on the models of training and qualification of conservators-restorers. Some argue that specialised training is indispensable to obtain highly specific, hands-on and up-to-date theoretical-practical know-how, and consider generalist training as a utilitarian approach that transforms the conservator-restorer into a “jack of all trades”, but effectively a master of none. Others, however, support the generalist approach as more suitable for the sector's sustainability and professional development, through a principle of adaptability based on consolidated increment of knowledge and tools, where professionals operate in an osmotic relationship of exchange.

Accepting the inherent and etymological nature of the concepts, how can we design specialist or generalist approaches, and what variables or coexistences might exist? Does a specialisation imply a greater sense of accountability and competence in a material, typology, or another specific area? Would it make sense, considering the need of a specialisation, to transform the generalist approach into a specific specialisation, where the scope of action is broader, focusing on prevention, and mediation with other areas and professionals, directed towards transdisciplinary projects with a more diversified and adaptable theoretical-practical background?

Is it enough to consider a conservator-restorer as a specialised professional at master's degree, despite the lack of substantial and consolidated professional experience? Does the professional need to obtain further skills, knowledge, and experience to be recognised with expertise in a particular area? If so, would it call for a professional recognition process?

When analysing the professional and educational landscape of the sector in Portugal (and ultimately Europe), all these questions have pragmatic, structural implications, reflecting concerns that were critically analysed in the discussion of the reformulation of specialisations within ARP.

Specialisations in Conservation-restoration under Portuguese Legislation

Portuguese regulation concerning Conservation-restoration is generally linked to the legal framework of national cultural heritage (Cultural Heritage Framework Law – Law No. 107/2001, 8 September). And in particular to the regulatory framework concerning legally protected heritage, whether held publicly or privately (Decree-Law No. 140/2009, 15 June), and that of public museum collections (Portuguese Museums Framework Law – Law No. 47/2004, 19 August). Further regulations are expressed in other diplomas, such as those for archaeological and archival heritage¹². Within the Portuguese legislative context, the term “specialisation” appears in the regulatory lexicon¹³, but there is no formal list or regulative definition of such specialisations in Conservation-restoration. Organisations, institutions, companies, and professionals in the sector operate with specific categories (material, functional, typological among others), which are recognised nationally and mirror similar ones at European and International levels. These categories, or specialisations, stem from the historical development of Museology and Conservation-restoration within the national

¹² Reis, David Teves (2023) Conservator-Restorer | Current Status of the Profession in Portugal. *Ensuring high quality in safeguarding Cultural Heritage* | ACAWA-GR Conference Proceedings, Athens, pp. 44-49.

¹³ In addition to the references to specialisation in the development law (Decree-Law No. 140/2009, of 15 June), there are also references in the basic regulatory framework, namely in the Cultural Heritage Framework Law (Law No. 107/2001, of 8 September): paragraph c) of paragraph 2 of Article 60 (“specialised technicians”) and paragraph 2 of Article 93 (“practice of material acts requiring specialised knowledge or tools”); and in the Portuguese Museums Framework Law (Law No. 47/2004, of 19 August), a legislative document considered by the Cultural Heritage sector to be in urgent need of updating: Article 46 (“specialised training”) and paragraph f) of Article 106 (“specialised staff”).

context, following a traditional classification system, and currently maintain an informal recognition stand within the legal framework of cultural heritage.

However, the legislation affirms the mandatory need for professionals with specialised qualifications, which is verified in practice by the assessment of academic curricula and professional experience. Thus, the application of the concepts of "specialisation" or "specialist" is common in Portuguese cultural heritage law¹⁴, but references are made in an extremely broad sense, with the evaluation of specialisations being linked to the existing academic context and referring to a national categorisation of heritage, all of them being informal frameworks.

The primary regulatory document for projects and interventions in cultural heritage (only for legally protected heritage) and, coincidentally, for the profession – Decree-Law No. 140/2009, 15 June – was recently amended to recognise the conservator-restorer as the qualified professional for the development of projects and interventions in protected cultural heritage. This law clearly validates defining principles of the specialist professional's profile and, following recent amendments, explicitly assigns to the specialised conservator-restorer the sole responsibility for such actions. We will further discuss this legislative change and how it demands an urgent discussion and regulation of specialisation processes and categories, as they are enforced by the Public Administration. Such dialogue must occur in close connection with the national higher education institutions for Conservation-restoration.

Specialisations in Conservation-Restoration Education in Portugal

In Portugal, specialised education in conservation-restoration exists, but the academic system (and consequently, the sector, both public and private) has been permeated by some arbitrariness, lacking clear and tailored requirements for formal acquisition of a specialisation, especially in the training programmes at the master's level.

The national higher education system¹⁵ recognises that specialised education is provided at the master's level (EQF7) and eventually further developed at a doctoral level (EQF8). However, the awarding of a specialisation is not always explicitly identified in diplomas nor in the internships' certificates, which hinders the identification of the specialisations established and provided by higher education institutions¹⁶. The idea that specialisation is determined only by internships or final dissertations becomes debatable when considering the weaknesses of this approach, especially in a sector that is increasingly demanding. This approach was also critically reflected upon during the reformulation of the specialisations recognised by ARP.

¹⁴ In Portuguese legislation related to the Cultural Heritage sector the term "expert" or any regulatory processes involving this definition do not apply. The status of expert is established in other areas, particularly those where the title is conferred by professional public associations or within frameworks governed by other legal regimes.

¹⁵ The framework of Portuguese higher education is regulated by the legal regime of higher education institutions (Law No. 62/2007, of 10 September) and the legal regime of higher education degrees and diplomas (Decree-Law No. 74/2006, of 24 March).

¹⁶ "After successful completion of a final examination the candidate is awarded a degree or diploma. A reference to the specialisms studied should be given." - E.C.C.O. Professional Guidelines; III (Education); II – Level of Education; p. 1.

In Portugal, higher education in Conservation-restoration is provided by three ENCoRE (European Network for Conservation-Restoration Education) member institutions¹⁷.

It is characterised by specialised training modules not integrated and articulated within a full specialised curriculum. In theory these learning processes are preparing qualified professionals to work directly in the labour market with a theoretical-practical approach conferring the necessary competences. The issue is whether these learning processes, as currently designed, are sufficient and actually deliver specialised training as the sector requires.

The Labour Market in Portugal

When analysing the current dynamics of academic specialisation applied to the Portuguese labour market, we observe that only certain areas effectively absorb specialised professionals: within national public heritage bodies and institutions, in the fields of intervention with a small number of specialised professionals or those required in public tenders for conservation projects. However, heritage authorities and bodies at local level hire professionals for non-specialised conservation-restoration positions. Often these public servants' jobs don't require a master's degree as mandatory. This is due to the fact of public services positions in Portugal are considered a general career path within the public administration, except for regulated professions.

Responsibility for managing projects in the conservation-restoration of protected cultural assets is set out in Decree-Law No. 140/2009, which demands professionals to have 5 years of professional experience after obtaining their academic qualification in the required area of specialisation. However, it can be observed that many active professionals with 5 years or more of practice struggle to prove their specialised experience. Their professional background is the result of a job market, both in the private sector and in some public institutions, that mainly promotes and seeks a more generalist practice of the conservator-restorer¹⁸. This hybridisation of skills, more or less generalist, combined with more specialised ones, is a growing reality. Even fewer are able to gain continuous and systematic experience in a specialised field without deviating into other areas over the course of their careers.

Indeed, the majority of the labour market itself, even in public sector roles, does not foster hiring specialist professionals, and this can be explained by four main reasons:

¹⁷ Of the three higher education institutions, two are part of the university sector (NOVA FCT - Faculty of Science and Technology of the Nova University of Lisbon and the School of Arts of the Catholic University of Porto - UCP), and one is part of the polytechnic sector (IPT – Polytechnic Institute of Tomar), all offering training in Conservation-restoration at EQF7 and EQF8 levels. However, without going into the specific characteristics and dynamics of each course, all these institutions provide training with a strong theoretical-practical component aimed at immediate integration into the job market.

¹⁸ “[...] *the competences and knowledge expressed at EQF levels 7 and 8 represent the specialism of the Conservator-Restorer only, not the broad field of Conservation-Restoration.* – E.C.C.O. Competences; p. 45. “[...] *the eligibility of someone entering the profession is expressed as: possessing the appropriate level of knowledge, skill and competence necessary to accept responsibility for Conservation-Restoration within a certain specialism or discipline and within the profession's ethical norms.*” E.C.C.O. Competences; p. 15. Statistical data on the profession in Portugal in “A empregabilidade no sector da Conservação e Restauro em Portugal” (2022); ARP [<https://arp.org.pt/2022/04/07/inquerito-emprego-e-empregabilidade-no-sector-da-conservacao-e-restauro-resultados/>]

1. The lack of public (and, to some extent, private sector) strategies promoting the long-term and conscious development of opportunities of and for specialised conservation-restoration practice.
2. Insufficient recognition of the real and evident needs for attaining an adequate level of specialisation, which is not solely related to the educational pathways, but is mainly due to the disconnection between education delivery and professional practice in ensuring in-depth specialised practice.
3. The absence of clear categories and a formal system for the recognition of specialisations in conservation-restoration.
4. The small scale of the heritage sector in Portugal. Regardless of the current activity observed in the labour market due mainly to external factors such as the EU RRF (Recovery and Resilience Facility), the sector is not structured with long-term synergies between labour market, sector needs, the suitability and long-term perspective of educational programs and models.

Thus, specialisations in Portugal have been awarded and recognised informally and unsystematically. Initially, the specialisation process occurs through a more focused academic path at the master's level (EQF7). Additionally, a growing number of professionals (about 15%) continue their training through doctoral paths (EQF8)¹⁹. However, it is mainly based on professional experience that the choice of one's specialisation is informally validated, frequently in an initial form of "self-assessment" and by peer assessment, given that there are neither defined criteria for a formal categorisation and awarding of specialisations nor an adequate system for evaluating specialised competencies²⁰.

Specialisations Recognised by ARP

In the process of revising the statutes and internal regulations of AR, carried out in 2019 and approved in 2020, the need arose to update the list of specialisations, as the specialisations recognised since 1995, without any changes, no longer adequately reflected the evolving professional practice realities and needs.

Considering that it is mandatory for ARP's members to select a specialisation based on the internship or final thesis in the academic context²¹, the revision process contemplated the possibility of allowing the choice of a second specialisation, considering their work experience in the sector. It is recognised that specialisation acquired by training should not limit the acknowledgement of a professional's

¹⁹ At the doctoral level, various pathways are pursued; however, there is a clear trend towards acquiring knowledge, tools, and skills with a stronger scientific focus, particularly in the areas of examination and analysis methods, material studies and diagnostics, as well as Art History.

²⁰ "Depending on national situations, it may also be relevant to assess professional practice to confirm the conservator-restorer's ability to work, ethically and competently in his/her specialism." - E.C.C.O. Professional Guidelines; III (Education); II – Level of Education; p. 1.

²¹ ARP's Internal Regulations: "Article 6 – Specialisations: 3 – The assignment of the corresponding specialisation to the initial training will be made as follows: a) Specialisation listed in the Official Gazette for graduates of the José de Figueiredo Institute; b) Area of pre-specialisation listed in the Certificate of Qualifications for graduates of the School of Conservation-Restoration; c) Specialisation carried out during the final curricular internship, evidenced by a declaration from the higher education institution or organisation where the internship took place, for members classified under points b) and c) of paragraph 1 of Article 4 of the Statutes; d) Specialisation associated with the master's dissertation title, in the case of members classified under point a) of paragraph 1 of Article 4 of the Statutes."

competencies in other areas. By considering paths and experiences in areas distinct from the initial academic specialisation, driven by the conditions and needs of the job market or by diverse professional career paths pursued voluntarily. This second area was accepted, being limited and conditioned, by the assessment of professional curricula and proof of two years of actual experience in the specialisation area in question²². This exception, widely discussed, acknowledges that the excessive ascription of specialisations to the same professional is counterproductive and contrary to the nature of the specialisation concept.

ARP thus attests that its members have a training that appropriately complies with the principles of E.C.C.O., but it cannot, at present, guarantee the full scope of a certification of specialisations. Currently, ARP's professional directory is the only one in Portugal that lists qualified professionals in conservation-restoration, categorised by areas of specialisation.

In the process of reviewing the specialisations recognised by ARP, an extensive study was conducted on international realities, including the analysis of categorisation of specialisations used by 13 European professional associations, including twelve E.C.C.O. member associations, the British ICON, and the American AIC, as well as the nomenclatures of the ICOM-CC (International Council of Museums – Committee for Conservation). In this study, approximately 16 categories, not yet used by ARP were identified, along with an equivalent number of subcategories.

There are considerable differences between the specialisations identified in different national contexts supported by their respective cultural, artistic, and historical realities, as well as the distinct needs of each cultural heritage ecosystem. Therefore, it was necessary to accommodate the specialisation areas to the specific needs of Portuguese heritage and law, while maintaining coherence with European specialisation areas, enabling mutual recognition of competences and qualifications, mobility of qualified professionals, and simultaneously adjusting the specialisation catalogue to the dynamic evolution of cultural heritage.

Process for the review of specialisations recognised by the ARP

2017	2020
Tile, Ceramic and Glass	Tile, Ceramic and Glass
Stone	Stone
Painting	Painting
Mural Painting	Mural Painting and Stucco
Textiles	Textiles
Paper, Documents, and Book	Graphic Documents
Polychromed Sculpture	Polychromed Sculpture and Gilded/Polychromed Woodcarving
Photography	Photography, Sound and Audiovisuals

²² ARP's Internal Regulations: "4 – The assignment of the second specialisation is intended for active members who develop a professional career in an area distinct from or in addition to their initial training. It should establish a relationship with the candidate's training process or result from the acquisition of skills and qualifications for that purpose; 5 – The definition of the second specialisation is the responsibility of the active member, but it must be consistent with the curriculum vitae submitted at the time of admission; 8 – The second specialisation requires 2 (two) years of actual work in the area requested as the second specialisation; 9 – For the purpose of proving the actual work referred to in the previous paragraph, declarations issued by the institutions and/or companies where the work took place must be submitted."

Musical Instruments	Musical Instruments
Metals	Metals
Furniture	Furniture
Archaeological Assets	Archaeological Heritage
Ethnographic Assets	Ethnographic Heritage
-	Industrial Heritage
-	Scientific and Technical Heritage
-	Contemporary Art
-	Preventive Conservation

The analytical process of reformulation and consolidation of ARP's specialisations resulted in a new classification of 17 areas of specialisation. Although conventional, the reclassification was thoroughly considered, updated, and aligned with the current evolution of the national sector, avoiding the fragmentation of specialisations into multiple subcategories.

It is acknowledged that the outcome of the specialisation review process still presents some deficiencies or limitations. However, the process is carried out with a positive balance, without disruption, taking into account the following considerations, constraints, and objectives:

1. **Inclusion of Non-traditional Specialisations:** The inclusion of specialisations outside the traditional classification (such as typologies, functions, or materials of objects) was carefully considered²³. Of those with operational nomenclature adopted in other international contexts only preventive conservation was introduced into ARP's new catalogue of specialisations, given the existence of academic study cycles and professional practice in this field.
2. **Contemporary Art as a Specialisation:** The introduction of Contemporary Art as a specialisation was grounded in the same principles: the existence of academic cycles and professional practice in the Portuguese context. A single specialisation was thus introduced for contemporary production, without typological or material distinction. This area considers new materials and techniques in artistic production and is adaptable to the rapid transformations within the Contemporary Art sector.
3. **Industrial and Scientific Heritage Specialisations:** The introduction of two new categories, Industrial Heritage, Scientific and Technical Heritage, acknowledges new areas of specialisation that were not previously included in the ARP catalogue. While these areas can be addressed together in various European and international contexts, they were divided in tandem with the distinct realities in the Portuguese labour market, especially within the museum sector.

²³ "New heritage, i.e. heritage characterised by novel material or immaterial cultural expressions, new modes of production and uses of technologies, presents fresh challenges to conservators-restorers and other professionals involved in the conservation process. Beyond the material, new heritage is also closely associated with the "third regime" of cultural heritage, which includes a value-oriented and inclusive approach requiring professionals to pay specific consideration to the immaterial aspects and meanings of the heritage. [...] Education & Training for new heritage in conservation-restoration has to take account of these aforementioned developments and incorporate them into curricula." - CHARTER (2024), Report: Dynamics and future scenarios for the cultural heritage sector; p. 76.

4. **Inclusion of Audiovisual Media:** The need to include sound and audiovisual media in the catalogue of specialisations was recognised, and it was aggregated with the previously existing Photography specialisation. This reformulation sought to incorporate better the reality of sound and image archives in Portugal, and current professional practice.
5. **Renaming of the Paper, Documents, and Book Category:** Adopting a nomenclature widely used in Portugal for this set of typologies and materials, the category "Paper, Documents, and Book" was renamed "Graphic Documents," considering it as a single area without distinction of sub-specialisations. This pragmatic adaptation was more aligned with the practical context of the specialisation in the labour market, sector institutions and the characteristics of the archives.
6. **Terminology Adjustments:** The term "assets" was replaced by "heritage" ("Archaeological Assets" became "Archaeological Heritage" and "Ethnographic Assets" became "Ethnographic Heritage") to better align with international terminology and to encompass not only material values but also immaterial ones.
7. **Introduction of the Stucco Specialisation:** A new specialisation in Stucco was introduced, adding to the existing specialisation in Mural Painting. This was justified by the aggregation of similar specialisation areas in the international context, and by the better adaptation of this specialisation in professional practice in Portugal, particularly with regard to urban rehabilitation.
8. **Polychromed Sculpture and Gilded/Polychromed Woodcarving:** The areas of Polychrome Sculpture and Gilded/Polychrome Woodcarving share similar material and formal aspects, and there are many professional paths that intertwine these two specialisations. However, Gilded/Polychrome Woodcarving, which includes altarpieces, was not listed in the previous catalogue. Given its significant importance in the sector, it was merged with Polychrome Sculpture, following current professional practice and how heritage assets are actually categorised in heritage institutions.
9. **Tile, Ceramic and Glass Specialisation:** the benefits of de-aggregating the subspecialisations were evaluated, however the existing Ceramic, Tile, and Glass category remained unchanged for reasons of convenience and consistency with curricula, the training reality in higher education, since it still represents current professional practice.
10. **Assessment Mechanisms for Specialisations:** The evaluation of specialisations remains as before: the specialisation of the internship area and/or final thesis of academic training as well as by professional practice. There is no intention or grounds to alter these in the current context. Nevertheless, the implementation of any formal recognition process regulating the profession, will require a decisive re-evaluation regarding the proof of specialised training cycles in higher education as well the proof of specialised professional practice.

Two years after the approval of the specialisations by the ARP, on 22 September 2022, the association organised an online roundtable nominated "*Higher Education in Conservation-restoration: Generalist*

or Specialist? What Model Best Serves Heritage and the Market in Portugal?” The event featured the participation of the presidents of ENCoRE and E.C.C.O., the representatives of the three universities offering conservation-restoration degree courses, and two private sector company directors. The objective was to discuss and reflect on the topic, considering both the normative documents produced in recent years, professional practice and sector dynamics, particularly after the pandemic crisis. Valuable reflections emerged from the discussion of existing issues faced by professionals, educational institutions, and their students. The importance of dialogue and cooperation between the academic and professional communities was also recognised. This debate further highlighted the urgent need for professional regulation, a process that finally gained legislative strength in 2024.

Professional Regulation Processes: Future Developments

The recent legislative amendment, published in November 2024 (Decree-Law No. 90/2024, of 22 November)²⁴ updated the legal regime for studies, projects, reports, works, or interventions on protected heritage, as in classified or soon-to-be-classified assets (Decree-Law No. 140/2009, of 15 June) (Fig.1). ARP’s board directly contributed to this process through consultation and drafting of the proposed amendment. The new legal framework clearly recognises the professional title, qualifications, and profile of the conservator-restorer, as well as their responsibility in these procedures, particularly in relation to movable and integrated (movable assets incorporated in immovable) heritage, and, more limitedly in immovable heritage²⁵.

Figure 1: 2021. Approval of Resolution of the Assembly of the Republic No. 188/2021, of 29 June, which recommends the Government to define the professional profile of the conservator-restorer, thereby ensuring the safeguarding of cultural heritage.

²⁴ Decree-Law No. 90/2024, of 22 November – “It amends Decree-Law No. 140/2009, of 15 June, defining the profile and qualifications required for conservators-restorers to carry out conservation-restoration interventions on cultural heritage.”

²⁵ In the previous version of the legislation, the responsibility of the conservator-restorer in interventions on immovable heritage was not properly identified. A new article has been introduced to clarify this: “Article 15-A - Works and interventions for the conservation-restoration of classified immovable property - 1 - The coordination and execution of works or interventions identified as conservation-restoration of immovable cultural heritage, as well as integrated movable heritage, are the responsibility of professionals with legally recognised qualifications and adequate experience in the respective area of expertise, in accordance with the provisions of Article 22.”

This formal recognition of the conservator-restorer's professional profile in Portugal. resolves two decades of ambiguity, during which professionals accountable for these procedures were vaguely referred as "*professionals with legally recognised qualifications*," in all legislation. This normative amendment, expressing the clear identification and accountability of the conservator-restorer, provides the necessary and urgent clarifications for the sustainability and quality of conservation-restoration practices in the heritage sector, establishing a solid foundation for future improvements in professional regulation processes.

The new legislation now assigns full responsibility for the project management and coordination of conservation-restoration works or interventions to a specialised conservator-restorer with discrete higher education and at least five years of professional experience after obtaining the academic qualification. Interventions of conservation-restoration are exclusively carried out by those with the specialised conservation-restoration qualifications at EQF7 level.

The professional title and status of the conservator-restorer are now recognised under Article 18, Paragraph 2²⁶, which ultimately is in accordance with the admission requirements set out in ARP's Statutes (Fig.2). The legislative update now makes the process of defining and recognising specialisations imperative and even more urgent. Paragraph 3 of Article 18 specifies that "*the higher education qualifications referred to in the previous paragraph and professional experience must be relevant to the respective specialisation area and the works or interventions concerned*", a premise reinforced by the stipulations on the authorship of the preliminary report necessary for approving and authorising works or interventions – Article 5, Paragraph 2 – and on the management and execution of works – Article 22, Paragraph 2. This debate has become even more critical in light of the transitional provision in the law – Article 4 – which establishes that "*within three years of the entry into force of this decree-law, professionals with at least 10 years of professional experience in the management and coordination of conservation-restoration works or interventions on movable cultural assets or integrated heritage, and who do not hold the legally required academic qualifications, may apply to the competent cultural heritage administration for recognition of their qualifications to carry out such functions.*" This legal provision entails a process of recognition of professional qualifications, where heritage public authorities with national and local competences are solely accountable for its implementation and resolution. The current proposal emanating from these authorities consists of various processes being carried out in parallel by different bodies addressing the different heritage typologies, sectors, levels of governance and with no articulated solution for the public and private sector.

ARP's stance is that it should be a single, transparent and standardised procedure, thereby impartially clarifying the profile of those already active in the labour market who don't have the established higher education profile, regardless of the typology of heritage they work with and at what level of governance they operate for. Otherwise, it will cause discrimination and inequality between

²⁶ "Article 18.º [...] 2 – "(Term) '*Professionals with legally recognised qualifications*' refers to conservators-restorers with a Bachelor's and Master's degree (post-Bologna) in Conservation-restoration, as well as other conservators-restorers with the following qualifications: a) Bachelor's (5 years) degree in Conservation-restoration prior to the Bologna process; b) Bachelor's (4 years) degree in Conservation-restoration with entry before 1997; c) Higher education courses in Conservation-restoration provided by foreign higher education institutions recognised by a national public higher education institution, in accordance with Articles 20.º to 22.º of Decree-Law No. 66/2018, of 16 August.

conservators-restorers working in the different subsectors, level of governance, as well as between those who operate in public and private sectors.

Figure 2: 2024. ARP's social media communication image celebrating the approval of Decree-Law No. 90/2024, of 22 November, which amends Decree-Law No. 140/2009, of 15 June, defining the professional profile and required qualifications of conservator-restorers for carrying out conservation and restoration interventions on cultural heritage.

This process of professional recognition, outlined by the current legal framework for the professional profile of the conservator-restorer, depends however on yet inexistent official categories for conservator-restorers' specialisations. Their definition would be a fundamental premise for the needed regulatory framework design and lead, eventually, to a comprehensive accreditation process. This can only be coherently achieved through a joint collaboration between the public authorities, educational institutions, and professional bodies. In reality, without this validation process, gaps will persist in the full application of the legislative framework due to a lack of effectiveness and supplementary regulation.

Acknowledgements

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to Mariana Cardoso and Rui Borges, former members of the ARP Board, whose valuable contributions were essential in the discussions on the specialisations in conservation-restoration during the revision process between 2019 and 2020.

References

1. E.C.C.O. (2011). *Competences for access to the conservation-restoration profession* (2nd ed.). E.C.C.O – European Confederation of Conservator-Restorers' Organisations A.I.S.B.L., Brussels.
2. E.C.C.O. (2002). *Professional guidelines: I – The profession; II – Code of ethics; III – Education*. E.C.C.O – European Confederation of Conservator-Restorers' Organisations A.I.S.B.L., Brussels.
3. ARP. (2022, April 7). *A empregabilidade no sector da Conservação e Restauro em Portugal*. Associação Profissional de Conservadores-Restauradores. [<https://arp.org.pt/2022/04/07/inquerito-emprego-e-empregabilidade-no-sector-da-conservacao-e-restauro-resultados/>]
4. Batz, W. (2019, January 18). "Academic studies and education in conservation-restoration – European perspective and overview 2018" [Conference session]. *In The Conservator Restorer: A Cultural Heritage Emerging Profession*; ARP; Lisbon, Portugal.
5. Reis, D. T. (2023). "Conservator-restorer: Current status of the profession in Portugal." *In Ensuring high quality in safeguarding cultural heritage* [Conference proceedings]. ACAWA-GR Conference Proceedings, 44-49.
6. Schneider, K. (2019, January 18). "Conservator-restorer in Italy: Progress, problems and opportunities in the transition to a regulated profession" [Conference session]. *In The Conservator Restorer: A Cultural Heritage Emerging Profession*; ARP; Lisbon, Portugal.
7. CHARTER. (2024). *Report: Dynamics and future scenarios for the cultural heritage sector* (p. 76). [<https://charter-alliance.eu/results/>]

Generalists versus Specialists: Education and Demands in Professional Secretary of Conservation-Restoration in Germany

Gisela Gulbins¹, Julia Brandt²

1. Conservator for decorative arts at the Reiss-Engelhorn-Museums Mannheim
2. Conservator for painting and polychrome wooden sculpture at Bavarian State Office for the Protection of Monuments

* Contact Author: gisela.s.gulbins@web.de

Abstract

The paper highlights the demands in the field of conservation-restoration in Germany from the perspectives of both museums and freelance professionals. In small museums, often only one conservator is employed, who must possess broad knowledge of various materials to manage diverse collections. Specialised treatments are typically outsourced to external experts. In contrast, larger museums require specialisation to meet scientific standards. In freelance practice, an efficient, pragmatic approach is essential, where overly narrow specialization can limit flexibility. During education more exchange between experienced professionals and academic institutions would be beneficial. Closer collaboration could promote innovation and practical learning. Overall, a balanced education is recommended—one that combines specialisation with interdisciplinary insights and research skills. Networking and lifelong learning are considered crucial for professional success in the field of conservation-restoration.

Introduction

The conservation-restoration sector is a heterogeneous field. Skills and competences needed can vary significantly depending on where a conservator-restorer is working. Libraries and archives for example require a different type of approach than museums. It makes a big difference if you work in a large museum with several conservators with different specialisations or if you work in a small museum with little staff and a varied collection. Freelance conservators can also work in different environments: private collections or galleries might require other competences than public museums or the heritage sector. The heritage sector in this case is defined as conservation-restoration treatments performed on listed monuments which in Germany can be publicly or privately owned. This article will focus on skills and competences required in mid-size to large museums and the

heritage sector as these reflect the background of the authors. Observations and proposals made are based on personal experience.

Demands in the heritage sector

In the heritage sector, freelancers primarily respond to public tenders and are often required to work on-site. Public tenders demand a straightforward and efficient approach, as deadlines are tight, and contracts are generally awarded to the most reasonable offer. Being too slow often means being too expensive or, if the contract is already awarded, incurring a financial loss for the conservator-restorer. Efficiency, combined with quality, requires experience and therefore a specialised scope of expertise. Large construction sites, where many different companies are involved, as well as working on-site in general, require complex planning and strong organisational skills.

Figure 1: Monstrance as an example of religious cult object cared for by conservators-restorers.

On the other hand, overly narrow specialisation can be a disadvantage, as it often leads to a lack of flexibility. For example, altar pieces can be a combination of various materials: polychromed and gilded wood for the architectural elements and sculptures, a central canvas for the painting, and in Catholic churches, reliquaries made of metal or glass that contain a mix of materials such as bones,

glass, precious stones, or wax. Chandeliers, silverware, and precious textiles may also be part of the ensemble.

The owners of these artworks are often unfamiliar with conservation-restoration treatments or specific areas of specialisation. A priest who plans to restore the altar of his church may only undertake such a task once in his career. The same is true for the owner of a historic house or castle. For them, the artworks are often not only seen as objects of artistic value but also as items of worship or as part of the home's furnishings. In such cases, they may prefer to hire one trusted conservator-restorer or a single company, rather than multiple specialists.

In these situations, it is crucial that the conservator-restorer is confident enough to carry out basic treatments on objects from related specialisations but also knows when a task is beyond their area of expertise. For instance, dry cleaning of a reliquary by a painting conservator might be perfectly fine, but mending broken elements on a reverse glass painting that is part of the same reliquary should be handled by a specialist in that area.

Some objects are not easily attributed to a specific specialisation (Fig.1). Painted stone sculptures or paintings on iron supports are commonly found in churches or historic houses. Depending on what is most damaged—the support (stone or iron) or the paint layer—either a stone/metal conservator or a painting conservator should take the lead. However, in nearly every case, advice or hands-on assistance from a colleague with expertise in the other area will be necessary. A strong network of colleagues with diverse backgrounds is a significant advantage when working in the heritage sector. In places of worship such as churches or synagogues anthropological and cultural factors also play a role in the treatment. Objects might only be touched under supervision and every alteration, even due to cleaning, should be agreed upon with the owners. Cultural and religious sensitivity is an important competence when working in religious places.

A significant challenge in the heritage sector is the lack of certain specialisations, such as metal, textiles, glass, and, to some extent, furniture. Since conservation-restoration is not a protected profession in Germany, anyone can work in the field, including on protected monuments. Over the past decades, a fairly high standard in conservation-restoration has been achieved through the education of owners and the use of good examples. Due to the shortage of specialists in above mentioned areas, it is becoming increasingly difficult to advocate for a qualified workforce. Construction companies and other less qualified firms are filling the gaps. In the long run, this may lead to a decrease in standards, at least in some areas of conservation-restoration.

Demands in the museum sector

As a conservator working in a museum different types of skills are needed. Usually, conservators are responsible for the organisation of object storage (Fig.2). Only few houses employ a depot manager; therefore, a good knowledge of preventive conservation and pest management is crucial. They should know what climate values are suitable for the stored collections, what packaging material should be used and how a pest infestation can be prevented, detected and treated.

Figure 2: A conservator-restorer is packing up rod puppets for storage.

Often, they have to take care of a permanent exhibition, but they are also responsible for setting up and dismantling objects for temporary exhibitions. That includes skills in mount making and the knowledge of how to write a condition report. They also have to ensure suitable climate and lighting conditions for the exhibits, inside and outside the showcases.

Especially at small and middle range institutions there are not enough conservators to cover every specialisation. It is not uncommon for only one staff position to be designated for conservation-restoration purpose. Therefore, the employee not only needs the ability to work independently and to be able to organise oneself, he or she often has to take care of a wide range of objects. Thus, a broad understanding of different materials is essential. Conservators should recognise the needs of an object even if it is not a material or type of object they know well, but they should have a good self-

assessment of when to treat an object themselves and when to call in an expert. Seeking the advice of colleagues to evaluate the situation better could be preferable in this setting. Then, conservators at a museum should be able to select the right experts and to accompany their freelance work.

When treating an object, the aim and the extent of the measures often have to be discussed with curators. Sometimes the opinions on a matter could differ. In these cases, good diplomatic skills could be very helpful in reconciling the curator's visions and the conservation needs of the object.

At larger museums there are often research projects that require conservators-restorers with scientific background. That may include knowledge of artists' working methods, a certain manufacturing technique, determination of age or evaluation of authenticity. Conservators therefore have to know how to conduct a research project, be familiar with different scientific examination methods and be able to interpret the results. For this work but also for decision-making in conservation a solid background in cultural history is important.

A ritually destroyed weapon, for example, should not be mended. If an artist used perishable materials like food, his or her artistic intentions should be ascertained. Should the material, once deteriorated, be replaced, conserved or should the loss be accepted as part of the concept?

Not only the cultural history but the history of every object is crucial for the decision which conservators take in their treatments. For instance, not every cup with an old repair should be restored; maybe it shows the particular value of the vessel for its previous owner. An archaeological vase with incrustations should not necessarily be cleaned, maybe it was collected because of this aesthetic aspect and served as a motif for a painter. Also, signs of wear and scratches could show the way an object was used and should not be removed.

Conclusion

A conservator-restorer needs many different skills to be prepared for the various challenges of the profession.

- A good foundation of knowledge of the different materials is very helpful if one has to deal with a broad variety of objects. Additionally, a more in-depth knowledge of one category of objects or of one material enables the professional to do more specialised work if required
- If a conservator-restorer wants to become self-employed he or she should have a clear idea of how to start and run a business.
- When working in a museum, collection management is one of the main challenges of a conservator-restorer. It is possible to specialise in this field and start a consulting business for heritage institutions.
- The academic studies should enable one to deal with all kinds of scientific challenges, and how to approach a topic that is not familiar to you.
- Another aspect of the professional life of a conservator-restorer are soft skills like the ability to adapt to the circumstances even if they are not ideal and to make the most of it. This applies for example when working on an excavation site abroad and when the materials one is used to are not available.

- The capability to work independently and to be well organised proves to be helpful in many scenarios as well as the ability to build professional networks. Knowing whom to ask always provides a conservator-restorer with a good support.
- When working in a team one has to find a compromise between different opinions and points of view. Hence, good diplomatic skills, like in many professional environments, are an advantage.

Summing up, we still believe that specialisation is a key to ensuring both efficiency and high standards in conservation-restoration treatments. General knowledge about various materials can be taught through a materials science approach, in addition to teaching students how to access relevant information and the latest research on conservation-restoration topics.

Potential for improvement in German education of conservation-restoration

The authors believe that university curricula in Germany already provide a solid foundation for a successful career. However, not all the skills and competencies mentioned above can be taught during a university programme. This is partly because students often do not yet know in which direction their career will develop, and partly because including all these aspects would further overload the curricula.

Business-related topics, for example, are only relevant for some and are often more effectively learned when they become practically necessary—such as when starting a business.

Certain skills and competencies can only be acquired through "on-the-job" experience or lifelong learning opportunities such as courses, workshops, and conferences. This is where we believe associations and educational institutions should collaborate more. Mentoring programmes that pair experienced professionals with recent graduates could ease the transition into working life.

Courses or workshops—offered by either universities or professional associations—could be designed for both students and practising conservator-restorers. This would allow experienced professionals to benefit from the latest academic research, while students could gain valuable insights from real-world experience and benefit from networking opportunities. Summer schools or joint work projects could also offer excellent opportunities for students to gain hands-on experience and see conservation-restoration in practice.

The current lack of certain specialisations such as textiles, metal, glass and furniture could be addressed by encouraging students to focus on areas that are less saturated in the job market. These specialisations often offer better financial prospects—something students may not consider when beginning their studies, but which typically becomes more important as they near graduation.

The Education of Restorers in Istituto Centrale per il Restauro. Final Intersectoral Trainings for the Convergence of Knowledge

Marco Bartolini, Francesca Capanna*, Giorgio Sobrà
Istituto Centrale per il Restauro (Rome, Italy)

* Contact Author: francesca.capanna@cultura.gov.it

Much has changed since the founding of the Istituto Centrale per il Restauro when its school was conceived to an audience of future professionals capable of working on all classes of materials. Since then, this approach has evolved towards sectorial education, also in the Italian regulations for the profession.

Nevertheless, at ICR we consider it fundamental to develop a common grounding of theoretical foundations and approaches to all cases of conservation intervention. This is the reason why ICR students participate in a common theoretical-practical activity. This imposes that the students share the knowledge acquired separately during the first years of study.

This type of cross-curricular training has been implemented in the context of works belonging to open-air museums of contemporary art, where the heterogeneity of the materials represents a suitable terrain for exchange between students. These cross-curricular activities are short-lived, but the osmotic exchange between individuals yields excellent effects.

Much has changed since the founding of the Istituto Centrale per il Restauro (ICR, 1939), when its pioneering school for restorers was conceived to impart general, theoretical and methodological notions to an audience of future professionals capable of working on any class of materials. In fact, this approach has progressively evolved towards sectorial education, concomitantly orienting the writing of current regulations in Italy, which today prescribe for restorers the obligation to obtain a master's degree through a five-year, single-cycle course of study.

Introduction

In Italy, the education in Restoration is divided into six distinct curricula: homogeneous macro-areas based on the criterion of the different classes of constituent materials of the cultural heritage. Nevertheless, at ICR we consider it fundamental to maintain, as a common and undivided baggage, solid theoretical foundations and approaches to the intervention, indiscriminately applicable to each specific case. This is the reason why, in the fifth year of the course, ICR students from all active

education curricula participate simultaneously in a common theoretical-practical activity. This allows - or rather imposes - highly specialised knowledge acquired separately during the first four years of study to be shared among the students themselves.

A case study, within those faced to implement this type of cross-curricular training, is that of works belonging to open-air museums of contemporary art, where the heterogeneity of the materials constitutes a very suitable terrain for this type of exchange between students, who must work together to find suitable solutions for the polymateric pieces treated. Conservation problems encountered on synthetic pictorial films applied to metal supports, on corten steel associated with deliberately combusted wooden elements, on cement plasters associated with plastic parts, are solved thanks to the interaction of students and lecturers of the different training courses. Activities of this type (and of the other examples that will be discussed) are generally short-lived, but the osmotic effect among each individual's experiences yields excellent results, both in terms of appreciation during its execution and as spendability in the development of subsequent professional activity. With regard to the job opportunities for Italian graduates, we will mention two critical elements in the national legislation: the first consists in the discrepancy between the subdivision of the restoration discipline into educational pathways and the organisation of the distinct professional registers; the second in the fact that there is still no standard regulating a post-graduate training pathway in the specific sector of Restoration of the Cultural Property, as instead exists in other European countries.

Today, the teaching of the subject of restoration in Italy is divided by law into six distinct courses of study.²⁷ Such regulation was developed in recognition of the need to subdivide the now extensive knowledge of the subject into coherent macro-areas of education, based on the classification of the different classes of materials that make up the cultural heritage. This manner of organising the curricula of the Scuola di Alta Formazione e Studio (In English, the School of Higher Education and Study) of the Istituto Centrale per il Restauro (abbreviated SAF-ICR), is however quite recent. In the current paper we will illustrate how the original notion of a course designed to impart general, theoretical and methodological concepts to an audience of restorers capable of working on any class of materials, has evolved towards sectoral training, and how this has occurred in parallel with the drafting of the regulations currently in force.

As is well known, the first restoration courses organised by Giulio Carlo Argan and Cesare Brandi at the time of founding of the ICR were aimed at transforming an essentially empirical and artisanal trade into a profession, based on technical-scientific and historical knowledge.²⁸ Less well known, however, are the steps that took place in the following years, when as this knowledge expanded, the need emerged for the preparation of increasingly specialised professional figures.

²⁷ Ministerial Decree no. 87 of 26 May 2009 currently in force, identifies the following Professional Training Pathways: PFP 1 Stone materials and derivatives; decorated surfaces of architecture; PFP 2 Painted artefacts on wooden and textile support; carved wooden artefacts, wooden furniture and structures; worked, assembled and/or painted synthetic artefacts; PFP 3 Textile and leather materials and artefacts; PFP 4 Ceramic, glass and organic materials and artefacts; metal and alloy materials and artefacts; PFP 5 Book and archival materials; paper and parchment artefacts; photographic, cinematographic and digital material; PFP 6 Musical instruments; scientific and technical instruments and tools.

²⁸ As Giulio Carlo Argan stated: "The training of restorers cannot be, as it once was, generically artistic or even only technical, in the sense of empirical experience; but must be both technical and historicist." ARGAN 1938-39, P. 134.

The first important step in this direction was taken on 2 February 1963 - some twenty years after the founding of the ICR and a decade after the enactment of the implementing regulation of the founding law²⁹ - when the Directorate General for Antiquities and Fine Arts of the Ministry of Education established the "Commission for Changes to the ICR".³⁰ Although the commission met several times and discussed various proposals, it did not produce concrete results. Still, the reports on file in the ICR archives lucidly describe the discussion of critical issues, among which the recognition of the need for more specialised training curricula. Although such development would not find definitive resolution until the end of the century, some first ad hoc measures were taken at the end of 1969, when the then ICR Director, Pasquale Rotondi, with the Deputy Director of Studies, Giovanni Urbani, were allowed to modify the announcement for the 24th competition for admission to the School of Restoration. In that announcement, a number of places were reserved in a study path specifically dedicated to the conservation of metals and antique furnishings, alongside an already existing pathway concentrating on the conservation of paintings. Probably due to the experimentation of the two distinct sectors, only six places were advertised instead of the usual ten, distributed as follows: three students (including one non-Italian) for the sector of "Conservation of Metals and the Various Constituent Materials of Antique Furnishings", and six students (including two non-Italians) for the sector of "Conservation of Paintings".³¹

Rotondi and Urbani must have been satisfied with the experiment, as on 11 May 1970, when the Institute delivered an outline of proposed amendments to the 1955 regulations to the Museums Division of the Directorate General, the introductory comments reported on the 24th admission competition, highlighting the experimental implementation of the double program. The ICR proposals suggested what were essentially only minor changes to the previous regulation, being called "Amendments to the Regulation of Restoration Courses",³² however the document confirms the intention to formally introduce the second study area on metals and constituent materials of antique furnishings. Although the proposals remained a dead letter in the offices of the ministry, the ICR reiterated the request for revisions in the years that followed, and meantime continued the two study courses.

While the legislative process aimed at amending the ICR regulations remained stalled, the debate on education in the field of cultural heritage conservation continued lively. In the 1980s, new degree courses in the "Conservation of Cultural Heritage" came into being. The first, of experimental character, in the Faculty of Humanities at the University of Udine, introduced teachings of a scientific nature, informing on materials and their behaviour in interaction with the environment. At the same time, the National Research Council, when restructuring its national advisory committees, included one expressly dedicated to technologies for cultural heritage. In 1987, at the close of the national conference "Problems of Restoration in Italy", organised by the CNR itself, study groups were set up

²⁹ Presidential Decree No. 1517 of 16 July 1955 (Regulation of the three-year course and the advanced training course) implementing Law No. 1240 of 22 July 1939

³⁰ BON VALSASSINA 2006, p. 71. Pasquale Rotondi, Cesare Brandi, Pietro Romanelli, Selim Augusti and Ugo Procacci were invited to join.

³¹ ICR Archivio Generale Storico – Busta: 1964-1973 III C p g dal XIX al XXVIII corso, Fascicolo: 1968-69 III C pg XXVI corso di restauro, Bando di concorso 30 giugno 1969, Foglio autorizzazione prot. 1903 del 16 July 1969.

³² ICR Archivio Generale Storico – 1970-1973 Busta Corso di restauro pratica generale fascicolo nuova proposta regolamento, Foglio prot. 1220, 11 May 1970.

with the task of drawing up papers on a series of topics. Among these was a group tasked with reporting on the national situation in the field of restorer training. The resulting report emphasised the need to adapt training courses in restoration to the complexity of the discipline and, for this purpose, proposed seven paths of study.³³

New vigour was given to the reform process with the institutionalisation of courses for restorers at the Opificio delle Pietre Dure (OPD) in Florence, in 1992. Article 4 of Law no. 57 of 20 January 1992, concerning the establishment of the School of Restoration at the OPD, foresaw the issuing of a government regulation for the ordering of that school, which would then also obviously be justified for the ICR courses. Thus, starting in 1996, the Institute, then directed by Michele Cordaro, resumed the forceful advancement of proposals for a new regulation, submitted simultaneously to the central offices of the Ministry and the trade unions. This time the request was for regulations with more substantial and incisive changes, finally aimed at bringing the restoration courses of the Institutes, by then part of the Ministry of Cultural and Environmental Heritage,³⁴ up to university level.

Leaving aside the many other innovative aspects of those proposals and of the regulation that followed in 1997,³⁵ our current intent is to focus on the aspect of sectoralisation of studies. A specific article in fact sanctioned the establishment of three sectoral specialisations: A) "Mural paintings, stuccoes, stone sculptures, paintings on canvas, on fabric, on leather, on paper, and polychrome wooden sculptures, surfaces and materials of architecture;" B) "Metals, ceramics, glass, enamels, gold, ivory, bone, amber and excavated objects;" C) "Mosaics, stone, natural and artificial materials." It also stipulated that "the areas could be modified or enlarged on the proposal of the teaching council, after consulting the competent sector committees of the National Council for Cultural and Environmental Heritage." By virtue of this paragraph, the ICR set out a fourth specialisation beginning

³³ The report states: "The growing technical, cultural and scientific complexity of the subject of conservation makes it necessary to have different training courses; real areas of specialisation divided into several classes of artefacts, classes that are similar in terms of technical convenience but sufficiently diversified to guarantee an adequate level of training. [...] For illustrative purposes, a series of areas is proposed here:

- (a) wall paintings, stone materials, mosaics, stucco, decorative terracotta cladding;
- (b) paintings on wood and canvas, polychrome wooden sculpture, wooden artefacts in general;
- (c) ceramics, porcelain, glassware, glazes;
- (d) metals and alloys: statuary, weapons, armour, jewellery;
- (e) book and documentary materials: manuscripts, books, archival documents; drawings, engravings, watercolours; paintings on paper and membranous media;
- (f) tapestries, carpets, embroidered, appliquéd, painted etc., fabrics in general;
- (g) musical instruments, distinct classes according to their constructional and mechanical characteristics: violin making, keyboard instruments, aerophones and organ making.

For artefacts and materials such as wet cloth and wood, fossil finds, poly-material artefacts in general, photographic and audio-visual materials in general, etc., consideration will have to be given as to whether special areas will be provided or whether postgraduate specialisation courses will suffice." NIMMO 1988, pp.115-120. Note how the areas correspond quite closely to those identified in Ministerial Decree 87/09, see footnote 1. The study group coordinated by Mara Nimmo, Istituto Centrale per il Restauro, was composed of: Lidia Branchesi, National Association of Art History Teachers; Gian Luigi Colalucci, Vatican Museums Restoration Laboratories; Anna Maria Dolciotti, BAAAAS Central Office; Enrica Fiandra, BAAAAS Central Office; Piero Gagliardo, Artistic Education Inspectorate, Ministry of Education; Luciana Giovannelli Vella, Central Institute for Book Pathology; Maria Lilli Di Franco, Central Institute for Book Pathology; Antonio Papa, Center for Photo-reproduction, Binding and Restoration; Rosanna Pavoni, Bagatti Valsecchi Foundation, Milan; Giorgio Torraca, Faculty of Engineering, 'La Sapienza' University, Rome. Secretariat Cristina Coldagelli.

³⁴ Law No. 5 of 29 January 1975, Conversion into law, with amendments, of Decree-Law No. 657 of 14 December 1974, concerning the establishment of the Ministry of Cultural and Environmental Heritage. (OG n.43 of 14-02-1975).

³⁵ Presidential Decree no. 399 of 16 July 1997 "Regulations on the Scuola di Alta Formazione of the Istituto Centrale per il Restauro".

the following year: D) "Textiles".³⁶ There was thus a response to the need for greater specialisation, but it was equally clear that the subdivision of teaching subjects had been based on past customs, rather than on a serious criterion of rationalisation as had in fact been proposed by the CNR study group of 1987.

The introduction in 2004 of a new National Code of Cultural Heritage and Landscape, including clear provisions on the competences and training of cultural heritage restorers in Article 29, represented a turning point. In the following years, a special working group was assigned to draft the relevant implementing decree of the Code,³⁷ for which one of the more delicate questions concerned the best division of training courses.

The starting point was a re-examination of the seven study paths proposed by the CNR group coordinated by Mara Nimmo. On that basis, the 1997 SAF-ICR Regulations underwent robust corrections. Address A, for example, was seen to deal with too many types of artefacts, diverse in their constitutive nature, and therefore requiring an abnormal concentration of theoretical support courses, especially in the natural sciences.³⁸ A major step was also to shift the restoration of wall paintings to section C, which predominantly included artefacts of an inorganic nature and into which all so-called "decorated architectural surfaces" were converged, thus separating them from the other types of paintings, predominantly on supports of an organic nature, such as canvas or wood. Finally, organisation according to constituent materials prevailed, so much so that even paper used as a support for painting, and not only as a constituent element of books and archival documents, passed into a specific path.³⁹

The results of this work were incorporated into Ministerial Decree No. 87 of 26 May 2009, which is still the reference standard for the definition of the criteria and quality levels for university-level training of the Restorer of Cultural Heritage, and which defined a total of six distinct specialised professional training courses based on the constituent materials of the artefacts, three of which were activated at SAF-ICR.⁴⁰

Having concluded this historical overview of the reasons for the institution of the different training courses, it seems appropriate to emphasise how the primary objective of restorer training remains that of reinforcing the common foundations, both theoretical and methodical, applicable to every type of object. Within the realities of training and careers, especially towards their final years and among recent graduates, what typically emerges is that the restorers find themselves dealing with complex and composite cultural assets, difficult to unequivocally categorise in terms of the

³⁶ This concerns in particular Article 9 of Presidential Decree 399/1997.

³⁷ The Ministerial Decree cited in footnote 9.

³⁸ Evidence of this historic problem can be found in the photocopies left behind by previous classes and still present in the files of the ICR, filled with notes in the margins: indications of anxiety over artefacts composed of materials that should, without doubt, have been addressed in section C, rather than section A.

³⁹ Today identified as number 5: see the subdivision into Training Paths noted in footnote 1.

⁴⁰ The ICR is currently accredited for training in the pathways: PFP 1 Stone materials and derivatives; decorated surfaces of architecture and PFP 2 Painted artefacts on wooden and textile support; sculpted wooden artefacts; wooden furniture and structures; fabricated, assembled and/or painted artefacts in synthetic materials (in the two venues of Rome and Matera) and in PFP 4 Ceramic, glass and organic materials and artefacts, metal and alloy materials and artefacts (at the Rome site only).

constituent materials characterising the training courses. For this reason, since the establishment of the university-level courses, the SAF-ICR has consistently dedicated some of the training credits of the fifth year of studies to so-called “specialised multidisciplinary seminars”: moments of in-depth application, shared by the students of the various training courses and oriented towards addressing issues of common interest.

In this way, all SAF-ICR students maintain a common and undivided grounding of solid theoretical foundations, and in their method of approach to intervention, applicable to all specific cases. On this basis, in fact, the students are obliged to share the highly specialised knowledge acquired separately during their first four years of study, in the three training curricula taught by the School of Advanced Training and Study.

Figure 1: Workshop on the technique of papier-mâché made freehand and moulded (SAF-ICR) at the two campuses of Rome and Matera.⁴¹

The first intake of students under the new system of the Ministerial Decree of 2009 arrived at their final year in 2015, and it was this class, the 61st of the SAF-ICR, that participated in the first experimental application of the multidisciplinary seminars. This students of this intake, participating in training pathways 1 and 4, were required to join their colleagues from training pathway 2, then in

⁴¹ For some notes on recent SAF-ICR training activities at the Rome and Matera sites see: CAPANNA, GENNARI, MORO, SOBRÀ, CASO 2020, pp. 605-618 and CAPANNA-SOBRA' 2024, pp. 534-546.

their fourth year, for participation in a theoretical module on “Techniques of Restoration of Manufactured, Assembled and/or Painted Synthetic Materials”.⁴² This was a module focusing on the materials used in the production of contemporary art, in particular pigments and their binders of modern synthesis, often applied on supports of an inorganic nature, such as wall surfaces.

The following year, the students of the 62nd course, taking training pathway 2, who in the previous four years had dealt with the restoration of paintings on predominantly wooden and textile supports, consisting of small and medium-sized movable works, participated an in-depth module on the use of these types of support materials for extensive architectural decorations, thus opening up the prospect of large-scale conservation planning and intervention. The title of the module was “Problems of Conservation and Restoration of Decorative and Functional Aspects of Historical Theatres”, where the decorated surfaces consist of carved and painted wood, painted canvases and, not infrequently, repetitive elements made of papier-mâché. The theoretical part of the course analysed, on the one hand, the contrasts between restoration and reconstruction in the cases of the Fenice Theatre in Venice and the Petruzzelli Theatre in Bari, both severely damaged by fire, and on the other hand, the planning of restoration interventions on very large decorated surfaces of architecture, in the case of the Teatro Sociale di Como.⁴³

Finally, the practical part of the module was devoted to a workshop on the technique of papier-mâché made freehand and moulded (Fig. 1). The very specific focus of this module was a great success among the students, enabling them to understand the scope of action to which the skills learnt during the five-year course is destined.

This convinced the SAF-ICR management that the shared seminar activity was the correct strategy for completion of study activities. For the students of the 63rd course, enrolled in pathways 1 and 4,⁴⁴ a new topic was therefore chosen in 2017, one that had been little dealt with in the four-year course, but which is increasingly the subject of the restoration profession: the conservation of works in concrete. In this seminar, titled “The Use of Concrete for Architectural Decorated Surfaces and Contemporary Monumental Sculpture: Problems of Conservation”, the theoretical module analysed the technical and conservation characteristics of concrete, as a material both for the creation of contemporary works and for use in interventions on architectural and archaeological objects.⁴⁵ The module was enriched by a study visit to Sicily, with three destinations: Selinunte, where concrete was formerly used in interventions for the anastylosis of ancient temple structures; the open-air museum “Fiumara d’Arte”, where concrete is the basis of most of the works of the collection; finally Gibellina, where following the earthquake of 1968, many of the projects for renewal - first and foremost the

⁴² See footnote 1.

⁴³ Speakers for the theoretical session included many highly qualified guests, in addition to the ICR technical-scientific staff: Donatella Ferrante, then MiBACT manager – Directorate General of Theatre; Alberto Artioli, then Superintendent for the Architectural Heritage and Landscape of Western Lombardy; Giovanni Nicoli and Valeria Villa, restorers at the University of Applied Sciences of Southern Switzerland; as well as Rita Rivelli, a freelance professional particularly experienced in the restoration of such artefacts.

⁴⁴ See footnote 1.

⁴⁵ Among the speakers for the theoretical session of the activity, in addition to the ICR scientific technical staff, several authoritative guests also spoke that year: Giovanni Carbonara, professor emeritus, and Simona Salvo both from the University of Rome La Sapienza; Ugo Carughi, president of Do.Co.Mo. Italia; Mauro Tommasini, technical director at MOST CND S.r.l.; and restorer Antonio Rava.

monumental "Cretto" by Alberto Burri - were realised using concrete. During these visits, in addition to technical learning, the students gained great benefit from meeting with the local communities, learning their perceptions of the monuments entrusted to them as professionals, and therefore the principles to be followed in striving for their preservation.

The recovery of the cultural heritage following tragic calamitous events is one of the founding tasks of the Istituto Centrale per il Restauro. The involvement of students in such activities has always been considered fundamental, both for the impact on the populations affected, for whom it is extremely consoling to see the commitment of young recruits towards the recovery of their heritage, and for the training of the students themselves, who encounter operational realities certainly different from those of the comfort of the Institute's well-equipped laboratories. This is why, in 2018, the students of the 64th course worked at the emergency depot set up by ICR in the Mole Vanvitelliana in Ancona. In that depot, the students, from training pathways 1 and 2, addressed the tasks of stabilisation operations on numerous works, highly varied in terms of materials, age and origin.⁴⁶

The students were able to observe the different morphologies of extreme damage caused to artefacts by the collapse of the buildings that housed them, such as, for example, the fragmentation of wall paintings (Fig. 2) and sculptures (Fig. 3) or the tearing of the canvas painting supports. They were also able to observe how works made from organic materials can suffer serious secondary degradation effects, mainly due to biological agents, in cases where recovery from the disaster site cannot take place in a timely manner and the object remains exposed to adverse climatic conditions. From this common experience the students drew important notions useful for planning first intervention activities in the event of a crisis, whatever their area of specialisation. They also carried out a contextual activity of filing and implementing data in the territorial "Risk Map" system, developed by ICR.⁴⁷

In 2019, the setting for sharing of learning by the students of the 65th course was the archaeological excavation of the medieval city of Cencelle, near modern Tarquinia in the province of Viterbo.⁴⁸ The module included several components: theoretical study of the entire site; practical activities of documentation, cleaning, consolidation and integration of masonry and flooring; documentation, recovery and first aid; intervention in the archaeological excavation of anthropological finds of burials; and finally storage operations, including research into containers and materials suitable for the correct preservation of each class of material.

This stimulating context of intervention allowed, on the one hand, the students who had studied the conservation of decorated surfaces of architecture (study path 1) during the four-year course to become acquainted with the working conditions and intervention problems connected with the excavation and recovery of stone, metal, ceramic, glass and bone artefacts. On the other hand,

⁴⁶ Three notable examples can be cited: the 16th century wall painting in fragments depicting 'Santa Lucia', from the Church of Santa Maria della Piazza in Gualdo di Castelsantangelo su Nera (province of Macerata); the 19th century painting on canvas depicting the 'Madonna with Child and Sacred Heart', from the Church of San Martino in Fiastra - Tedico (Macerata); and the 17th century wooden crucifix from the Church of Santa Maria Assunta in Pieve di Ussita (Macerata).

⁴⁷ See for example: CAPANNA-CACACE 2011, pp. 53-58 and CAPANNA-CACACE 2003, pp. 111-122 .

⁴⁸ Started in 1994 by Letizia Ermini Pani, supported by the Grandi Scavi programme of the Sapienza University of Rome, at that time under the direction of Professor Francesca Romana Stasolla. See also: VACATELLO 2023.

students who had already become acquainted with the reality of archaeological excavation and the restoration of the relative artefacts during the four-year period (study path 4) were able to carry out securing operations on in-situ painted plasters, masonry walls and on elements of collapsed stonework. The restoration and conservation of bone artefacts, at different levels of fossilisation, required joint application of the skills acquired in both training pathways 1 and 4.

Figure 2: A student treating one of the fragments of a wall painting after the collapse of the buildings that housed it.

The 2019 module also enabled mutual exchange not only between the ICR students of the different pathways, but also with university students of archaeology.

When the whole world came to a standstill in 2020, it became compulsory to avoid contexts of contact between individuals, and so no ICR interdisciplinary seminars were held in that year.⁴⁹

In 2021, while still observing strict rules of social distancing, the students of the different SAF-ICR training pathways from both locations (Rome and Matera) joined in a new project concentrating on 'Piscina Arte Aperta', an open-air museum of contemporary art near the city of Turin. In addition to the complex issues of conservation of artefacts in open air, the heterogeneity of the constituent materials provided very fertile ground for the exchange of knowledge among students. Among the conservation problems encountered were those of synthetic paint films applied to metal supports, of Corten steel associated with deliberately burnt wooden elements, and of cement plasters associated with plastic parts. These and still other problems were tackled and solved thanks to the co-

⁴⁹ Students were instead engaged in an online course in the use of software for the layout of their thesis work, distant from each other but unified in their goals of completing their studies.

participation of students and teachers from the different training courses and the reciprocal transmission of knowledge. The excellent results from the 2021 module led to the decision to organise those of the next three years in the same context of Piscina Arte Aperta.

Figure 3: A student treating a fragment of a sculpture.

The interdisciplinary seminars organised in the four-year period 2021-2024 are therefore the culmination of a long path of reflection on training in the discipline of restoration that, from the first considerations on the need for greater specialisation of training curricula, passing through the definition of the current regulatory framework, arrived at the conclusion that a final part of the training of future restorers must also pass through the spontaneous osmotic sharing between students of the various pathways, encouraged by complex and stimulating cases of application.

For the professional graduates from the ICR SAF, this training confirms the correct balance between specialisation and the ability to approach the work with a holistic vision and in line with general parameters, allowing them to work competently even in the context of shortcomings still extant in legislation on the subject. In the Italian context, in fact, public administrations are allowed to assign restoration work to professionals registered in a special list held by the Ministry of Culture. This, while ensuring a certain guarantee in the quality of interventions, is however organised in twelve sectors of competence that do not correspond to the six training courses. What happens, therefore, is that a table of comparison between the training courses and the ministry listings is used, but with only

approximate matching.⁵⁰ The hyper-subdivision into sectors of competence for the ministerial lists of restorers is moreover not backed up by the insistence on the use of these sectors in the rules of qualification for companies bidding on public works for assets protected under the Code on Cultural Heritage and Landscapes.⁵¹ What happens then is that young professionals are often called upon to work on materials that do not fully correspond with those to which they have dedicated their five years of study, and in this context, it is precisely their experiences of interdisciplinary sharing that enable these young professionals to correctly design their operations.

Italy, moreover, as this assembly is aware, is lagging far behind in the regulatory definition of the third level university study for the restoration of cultural heritage. We hope that a major breakthrough will come from the funding for the National Recovery and Resilience Plan, or PNRR.⁵² With these funds, innovative PhDs and PhDs for public administration and cultural heritage have been financed, and 3600 new PhD scholarships are being funded by the Next Generation EU over the three academic years beginning with 2022-2023. The Directorate General for Education, Research and Cultural Institutes of the Italian Ministry of Culture has joined the National Doctorate in Heritage Science project, which involves leading Italian universities coordinated by Sapienza University of Rome. This is a doctoral path, articulated in 11 interdisciplinary curricula, which aims to train a new generation of researchers and professionals in cultural heritage fields, able to collaborate and compete in the context of the most prestigious European and international initiatives. In this context, the Istituto Centrale per il Restauro has funded three scholarships for the 39th cycle, as well as four research grants and eight postgraduate scholarships for research on advanced and innovative materials for the conservation and restoration of cultural heritage. This should set a good precedent for bringing our nation up to par with other European training courses.

References

1. G.C. Argan, *Restauro delle opere d'arte. Progettata istituzione di un Gabinetto Centrale del Restauro*, in «Le Arti», 2 (1938-39), pp. 133-137.
2. C. Bon Valsassina, *Restauro made in Italy*, Milano, 2006.
3. M. Nimmo-L. Branchesi- G.L. Colalucci-A.M. Dolciotti- E. Fiandra-P. Gagliardo-L. Giovannelli Vella-M.L. Di Franco-A. Papa-R. Pavoni-G. Torraca, *La formazione professionale del restauratore*, in «Arte. Documento. Rivista di storia e tutela dei Beni Culturali», NN. 1-2 (1988), pp. 115-120.
4. F. Capanna-D. Gennari-F. Moro-G. Sobrà-M. Caso, *La formazione degli allievi SAF-ISCR in un cantiere didattico: l'intervento pilota sui mosaici della Casa del colonnato tuscanico nel Parco archeologico di Ercolano (NA)*, atti del XXV Colloquio dell'associazione italiana per lo studio e la conservazione del mosaico (Reggio Calabria, 13-16 marzo 2019), a cura di C. CECALUPO-M.E. ERBA, Roma, 2020, pp. 605-618.
5. F. Capanna-C. Cacace, *L'IsCR in Abruzzo*, in «Ananke» (nuova serie), 63 (2011), pp. 53-58.

⁵⁰ The table is published on the website of the Italian Minister of Culture <https://dgeric.cultura.gov.it/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/tabella-corrispondenza-settori.pdf> or

⁵¹ In 2017, the Ministry of Cultural Heritage (Mibact), in agreement with the Ministry of Infrastructure (MIT), issued Ministerial Decree No. 154/2017, effective as of 11/11/2017, which defined the requirements that companies must meet in order to qualify and participate in public works contracts involving assets protected under the Code on Cultural Heritage and Landscapes (Legislative Decree 42/2004), falling under SOA categories OG2, OS2A and B and OS25.

⁵² Plan approved in 2021 by Italy to revive its economy after the COVID-19 pandemic.

6. F. Capanna-C. Cacace, Il sistema Informativo Territoriale dell'ISCR, in *Il restauro in Italia, arte e tecnologia nell'attività dell'Istituto Superiore per la Conservazione ed il Restauro*, a cura di M.C. LAURENTI, Roma, 2013, pp. 111-122.
7. F. Vacatello, Cencelle VI. Una terra protesa verso il mare, Roma, 2023.
8. Capanna-G. Sobrà; Il restauro della grande decorazione architettonica. Recenti esperienze della Scuola di Alta Formazione ICR, in *Ingannare l'occhio "a meraviglia"*, a cura di E. ACANFORA, Bari, 2024, pp. 534-546.

A Discussion About What Specialisation Means Through the Example of Contemporary Art Conservation

Clémentine Bollard

Conservator and PhD candidate - EUR Humanités, Création et Patrimoine, UMR 9022 Héritages
CY Cergy Paris Université, CNRS, Ministère de la Culture (Paris, France)

* Contact Author: clementinebollard.ffcr@gmail.com

Keywords: Contemporary art; specialisation; training and practice in France.

Abstract

This paper addresses the training and practice of contemporary art conservation in France, in order to provide food for thought regarding specialities in conservation. Indeed, the impossibility to be technically able to conserve every material of which artworks are made, together with the predominance of concept over materiality for some of them, implies that contemporary art conservation consists first and foremost in understanding a singular context. In that respect, the competences of the conservator focus on establishing a framework for intervention rather than on the technical intervention itself.

Introduction

Like a specimen to be observed and analysed, or a playground on which to bounce ideas, contemporary art conservation is an ideal case study to provide food for thought regarding specialities in conservation.

This field - and this is already a first element; I won't use the term speciality, but the term field - is the one in which I practise and which I therefore know best, but it would have been just as relevant to mention the conservation of ethnographic cultural heritage, natural history collections or scientific and technical cultural heritage, which also include singularities that call into question the notion of "speciality" and its contours.

The specificity of these heritage sectors is that they pertain to types of collections or cultural assets that are not related to the typologies and techniques associated with Fine Arts - and we shall see that this is partly the case for contemporary art. In France, the typologies and techniques associated with Fine Arts have been used to frame "specialities" in trainings programmes in conservation of cultural

heritage⁵³. Therefore, how may the question of specialisation in conservation be approached in those fields that do not follow a logic based on materials or on manufacturing technique? How to deal with fields in which cultural assets are regrouped around a context, uses, and who bear a historical and social function which must imperatively be taken into account for their conservation?

In an attempt to provide some elements of reflection on this question, I will firstly discuss what it means to “specialise in contemporary art” by outlining the specific skills required to work in contemporary art conservation. Using France as an example, I will then look at how conservators are trained and how they work in this field.

What Does Contemporary Art Conservation Entail?

Contemporary art can be defined in two complementary ways which, brought together, highlight the range of characteristics that shape both the context in which they are created and the form of the works.

Contemporary art can first be defined chronologically, as a period in the history of art and artistic techniques. The chronological benchmarks for this period are usually 1945 to the present day, although these dates may vary. For instance, the Centre National des Arts Plastiques uses 1960 to the present and the Musée National d'Art Moderne in Paris uses the artist's dates of birth: the 'contemporary' collections include works by artists born between 1920 and 1960, whereas works by artists born after 1960 are part of the so-called 'prospective' collections. Works of art from this period therefore bear the marks of an era, and of political, socio-economic and technological contexts. The materiality of the works is characterised by the materials that this period generated. This includes most notably synthetic resins, which can be part of reemployed and/or assembled manufactured objects, or used for their intrinsic qualities.

A second definition is proposed by the art sociologist Nathalie Heinich⁵⁴ who suggests considering contemporary art as a singular artistic category which, within the chronological period mentioned above, does not replace but coexists with two other categories: classical art and modern art. Contemporary art, as an artistic category, would hence be an art of transgression - of the respective boundaries of art, the museum, authenticity, the law, etc. - an art that emancipates itself from the codes and standards previously used to define what constitutes a work of art. Classical art would rely “on figuration, respecting the academic rules of rendering reality”, while modern art would share “with classical art a respect for traditional materials (painting on canvas with stretcher, sculpture on pedestal), but would distance [itself] from it in that [it] is based on the expression of the artist's interiority”, i.e. “the personal and subjective character of [his] vision”⁵⁵.

⁵³ In France, four specific courses in conservation of cultural heritage were created between 1973 and 1983: the Université Paris I Panthéon-Sorbonne (1973), the Institut Français de Restauration des œuvres d'art (1977), which later became the restorers' department of the Institut National du Patrimoine, the École Supérieure d'Art d'Avignon (1981) and the École Supérieure d'Art et de Design TALM-Tours (1983). Today these training programs all deliver Master's degrees.

⁵⁴ Heinich, 1999, Heinich, 2022

⁵⁵ Heinich, 1999, p. 108

These definitions show that an infinite number of configurations, morphologies and materials constitute the field of possibilities for these “contemporary” works, notwithstanding the fact that their conceptual dimension may prevail over the material part of the work. The economists Nathalie Moureau and Dominique Sagot-Duvauroux have used this division into artistic categories to study the market for contemporary art and the “intermediaries”⁵⁶ who play a role in it⁵⁷. They have identified two models of social and economic organisation - a classical and a contemporary model - in which these three categories of contemporary artworks can be found, and which are based on different conventions for assessing the artistic qualities and values of works. They describe⁵⁸ a “contemporary model” based on the “originality of the artist's approach” and the discourse he or she uses, and a “classical model” for classical art, in which conventions are based on the “conformity of the work to existing models”. When it comes to artworks of the modern art category, the authors states that, depending on each case, their artistic qualities and values could alternatively be assessed through the classical or the contemporary model.

From a social and economic perspective, the distinction between a classical and a contemporary model can be used and extended to describe the organisation of work and the relational economy of intermediaries who are involved, not in the art market but in the making process of artworks.

The classical model of the making of artworks could be the one in which the artist uses materials - more or less classical - either alone or with the help of assistants, or has them used according to principles and techniques for which the codes and ecosystem of collaborators are fairly well identified because they have been practised for several centuries in relatively constant ways. These could be moulding a model, enlarging it, printing a plaster or cast proof, etc.

The contemporary model for organising the making of artworks could be one in which the artist creates the work, considering the use of a wide range of materials and techniques, but does not necessarily intervene in its implementation, and therefore in the making of the work, entrusting it to a network of collaborators.

These two models can be used to describe the type of organisation from which an artwork emerges, which will only be valid for that specific artwork because, while some artists adopt a single, constant model of creation and production, others move from one to the other as their projects evolve.

All these specificities of contemporary art, i.e. materiality, conceptual dimensions and economic production models, will in fact impact its conservation. Some artworks, in terms of conservation, will be consistent with a logic that we know quite well from other fields, such as Fine Arts; while others will affect and modify the ordinary frameworks and practices of conservation.

⁵⁶ On the notion of intermediary, see Chastel & Pomian, 1987, p. 5

⁵⁷ Moureau & Sagot-Duvauroux, 2010

⁵⁸ Moureau & Sagot-Duvauroux, 2010, p. 57

The Consequences of Contemporary Art Specificities on Its Conservation

Depending on the nature of the artwork, the impact on its conservation will be of a material and/or of a conceptual order. Not all materials and technologies can be conserved for more than a few decades, due to the inherent instability of materials such as synthetic resins and to the obsolescence of some technologies. Technically speaking, it is not always possible to conserve them and, furthermore, the works are sometimes not designed for the elements that make them tangible to be conserved.

The materials that constitute the artworks and the way in which they deteriorate must also be considered from a perspective that is specific to each case, this time for conceptual reasons. A contemporary metal artwork, for example, will not be treated in the same way as an archaeologically excavated metal object or a historical metal object. In the case of an archaeological object, as in the case of a contemporary artwork, we might seek to preserve the metal's corrosion products, but we would not do so for the same reasons, or in the same way. In the case of a contemporary artwork, we may not seek to stabilise active corrosion if this phenomenon was foreseen and desired by the artist.

We know the fundamental role of documentation in conservation, but in the context of contemporary art it is perhaps even more crucial, as in some instances what enables an artwork to exist is none other than this documentation. This is particularly the case for installations and artworks based on protocols. It may also be because the artwork's constitutive materials are evolving towards a certain and imminent end, and that the only way of preserving a trace of it is to document the object and its composition.

A last impact that the singularities of contemporary art have on its conservation process is linked both to the "contemporary economic model" for the making of artworks mentioned earlier, and to the overlapping temporalities of the creation and conservation of these artworks. The involvement of a multitude of people working alongside the artist, as he develops projects that may change from one work to the next, has changed the artist's role in understanding the materiality of his work: for sure, when he delegates the making of his works, he is no longer the only stakeholder and source of information. When conservation needs arise fairly quickly in the life of a work, the conservator will not only have to take into account the materiality and context of creation of the artwork. He will also need to communicate with the makers, as they sometimes hold technical information and know-how that will be useful for the conservation of the work, while ensuring that the artist's moral rights⁵⁹ are respected: he remains the sole author of the work, even if he did not manufacture the (entire) work himself.

Broadening the spectrum of post-creation stakeholders beyond those more traditionally present in the ecosystem of cultural heritage conservation professionals is induced by the fact that not all of these works are yet cultural heritage assets from the point of view of their legal status. There may be a coexistence between cultural heritage assets and heritage in the making, which remains very much alive! There is therefore a very strong value of contemporaneity or novelty, even for assets whose legal status places them in the field of cultural heritage, with the ecosystem of the making process

⁵⁹ Moral right exercised by himself or by his beneficiaries.

that is still present around the artworks and that must be taken into account in the conservation process.

The Skills Required to Work in the Field of Contemporary Art Conservation

The impossibility to be technically able to conserve each and every material of which artworks are made, together with the predominance of the concept over materiality for some of them, implies that contemporary art conservation consists first and foremost in understanding a singular context. As a consequence, the competences of the conservator will focus on establishing a framework for intervention rather than on the technical intervention itself.

Some works, in fact, involve a certain iteration of their component parts from the very start, and/or are the product of an industrial manufacturing process that can render traditional conservation operations pointless - not so much in terms of preventive and curative conservation operations, but in terms of restoration. How can elements produced by machine tools be reproduced or imitated by hand? Since it seems neither possible nor useful to master all the manufacturing techniques in order to eventually be able to remake certain elements, the fundamental skill is to have the capacity to identify the moment when the gesture of the conservator reaches its limits, and when it is therefore necessary to involve a professional with the required skills in the conservation project.

Figure 1: Diagram of the coordination role of conservator-restorer of the contemporary art

As the conservator cannot be “specialised” and competent to work on all types of materials or processes, he or she will consequently often play the role of project manager. If we consider the notions of field speciality discussed earlier, it becomes clear that to work in contemporary art conservation, it is necessary to master the ins and outs of the field from a theoretical point of view. Furthermore, while it is not possible to be technically competent in all the constitutive materials or processes, it is nevertheless possible to develop technical expertise in some of them. Evidently, this

technical expertise must be firmly embedded in an understanding of the theoretical and contextual issues surrounding the artwork being treated.

What Is the Approach to Conserving Contemporary Art in France, and How Are Conservators Trained?

From a quantitative study⁶⁰ carried out by Léonie Hénaut and Gaspard Salatko, sociologist and anthropologist respectively, we know that approximately 75% of conservation-restoration in France is carried out by self-employed people - mostly one-person businesses, less frequently small businesses with a few employees. The way the sector is organised has a significant impact on the way professionals present themselves, and on the types of assignments they are given.

How Do Conservators Present Themselves?

The 25% of professionals who work in cultural or heritage institutions most often say “I am a conservator at such and such place”. A specialisation may not appear very clearly, but a field or preferred area of expertise is implicitly expressed by the nature of the collections housed by their institution, or by the function and perimeters of this institution - in the case of research laboratories, for example. The same applies when they are in charge of a department, for while conservation skills and knowledge are certainly expected, specialisation is perhaps of less importance. Above all, the related qualities of project and team management, as well as the ability to create links with other departments within the establishment might be privileged over specialisation.

The professionals who are self-employed, therefore the vast majority in France, usually present themselves from the angle of their technical skills, rather than under the banner of their cross-disciplinary skills. This is because what potential clients are seeking from these professionals is first and foremost expertise in diagnosing and/or implementing conservation work. This is manifest in the specifications published in the context of public contracting, where the allotment or description of the profiles being sought follows this logic.

In the field of contemporary art, a clear and concise presentation is almost impossible because it would tend to be too imprecise. For instance, I present myself through a series of steps, first indicating that I work mainly with three-dimensional objects made of synthetic materials, and secondly that I work with various types of collections: Fine Art, design objects, fashion and costume collections, scientific and technical heritage. Other professionals have a much more cross-disciplinary approach to materials (synthetic materials and wood, synthetic materials and stone and plaster) but perhaps move less from one sector of collection to another, while others combine the two.

As far as professional associations are concerned, the organisation of the French section of the International Institute for Conservation’s working groups is based upon an approach by material: a

⁶⁰ Hénaut & Salatko, 2020

'modern and contemporary materials' working group⁶¹ has therefore been set up. The Fédération Française des Conservateurs-restaurateurs's online directory⁶² [10], uses 'speciality areas', proposing categories which combine materials, collection sectors and object types, including a speciality/area "contemporary art and materials". Each member of the association can indicate up to two areas of specialisation on their profile, a sign that it would be overly simplistic, if not impossible, to present oneself as a professional from a single angle.

There is a real 'à la carte' composition of one's professional activity, sometimes guided by centres of interest, sometimes driven by economic necessity and the need to conform to market demand. In terms of benchmarks for identifying the fields and specialities of conservators, a combination of cross-disciplinary skills, multiple skills and hyper specialisation is used, and we will see that for managers of contemporary collections, the challenge is to find a professional whose cross-disciplinary skills will enable him or her to take on the coordination of interventions.

What Kind of Work Organisation is Required for Conservation Projects Involving Contemporary Art?

The composite nature of certain works means that no-one is in a position to deal with a work on their own. Even small-scale projects sometimes require the formation of multi-disciplinary teams - a fact that we tend to see in the context of conservation projects on monumental heritage, for example, where teams from different specialities work alongside one another. A collection manager may consult several conservators, each of whom will reply "I can deal with this part of the work but not with the others", before one of them finally offers to take on the task of coordinating the work of the various specialists.

This type of project will therefore place the conservator in the position of project manager, or of a representative of the artwork's owner. Most of the time, the conservator will conduct a preliminary study, establish a diagnosis and define the objectives with the person responsible for the work, then coordinate the work carried out by conservators but also by other professionals. In such circumstances, the conservator becomes the coordinator of a project that brings together the traditional ecosystem of professions involved in the preservation of cultural heritage – curators, documentalists, archivists, scientists, mount makers, registrars, architects, etc. - as well as the ecosystem of the contemporary art-making model we mentioned earlier - the artist or his successor in title, the makers, material suppliers and so on. His/her role will be to ensure that the project runs smoothly, by acting as an interpreter between professionals from diverse lines of work, such as a museum curator and a paint manufacturer.

⁶¹ It should be noted that this covers an extensive range of materials, since the modern and contemporary materials category can - notably but not exclusively - include concrete, medium and synthetic resins, which themselves fall into the category of film-forming materials such as paints and varnishes, as well as all kinds of solids.

⁶² <https://ffcr.fr/liste-par-specialites>, accessed April 10, 2025.

How Are Professionals Trained - And Does the Training Meet the Needs?

Training Courses Dedicated to Contemporary Art Conservation

Twenty years ago, when I was looking to enrol in a conservation course, none of them offered specific teachings in contemporary art: the only way ahead was to learn through work placements in the field, with practising professionals, and then by choosing the subject for a final dissertation.

The four programs that deliver a Master's degree in France⁶³ have gradually developed this education, and now offer courses dedicated to contemporary art that they have integrated into their curricula, which vary considerably from one program to another.

Only the École Supérieure d'Art d'Avignon (ESAA) offers a specific 'contemporary art' orientation, alongside an 'ethnographic objects' orientation, and has developed a whole range of theoretical courses linked to conservation in these two fields. In terms of practical training, students have access to courses on a variety of materials (leather and skins, textiles, plaster, natural organic materials, metals, and synthetic materials, painting, etc.). The Université Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne offers students enrolled in the "three-dimensional objects" section a total of twelve hours of lectures and six days of practical work, spread over two years, on contemporary art. The Institut National du Patrimoine offers around twenty-four hours of lectures and practical work for students enrolled in certain specialities (sculpture, furniture, graphic arts, painting). The École Supérieure d'Art et de Design de Tours (ESAD TALM-Tours) offers around thirty hours of classes, divided between theory and practice. Internships and the choice of artworks/subjects for dissertations continue to play an important part in specialising in contemporary heritage matters.

Does the Training Offer Meet the Needs?

The answer to this question is not a simple one, because there is certainly a feeling that training could always be improved, and perhaps because this field of conservation is still very new. It does however seem fair to say that the conservation of contemporary artworks is being operated as well as it can be, in consideration with the challenges to which this field is exposed. It is quite clear that people who have already completed a degree in contemporary art history, or who have a marked interest in such artworks, will have an easier understanding of the specific nature of conservation of this type of cultural heritage. It is also certain that initial training in conservation is not everything: many skills are gained in practising conservation in the field, during the first few years of practice, and even long afterwards throughout a professional career.

Conclusion

In regard to the specialisation and organisation of courses, the case of contemporary art conservation-restoration seems to bear witness to the central role of theoretical courses. They enable a

⁶³ The practice of conservation is partially regulated in France, as these four programs are currently the only ones that deliver a diploma entitling their holders to work on the collections of the «Musées de France», in accordance with the provisions of articles L. 452-1 and R. 452-10 of the French Heritage Code.

conservation-restoration project to be constructed and adapted according to the singularity of each heritage context, leaving the acquisition of technical skills subordinate to an understanding of the contexts in which cultural assets are created and conserved.

The various points we have discussed perhaps also indicate that the coexistence of a diversity of curricula, with complementary approaches, especially when there are several curricula in the same country, can represent a real asset for the conservation of a plural cultural heritage that is likely to become ever more diversified in the future.

References

1. Chastel, A., & Pomian, K. (1987). Les intermédiaires. *Revue de l'art*, 77(3), 5-9. <https://doi.org/10.3917/rda.077.0005>
2. Heinich, N. (1999). Pour en finir avec la querelle de l'art contemporain. *Le Débat*, 104(2), 106-115. <https://doi.org/10.3917/deba.104.0106>
3. Heinich, N. (2022). *Le paradigme de l'art contemporain. Structures d'une révolution artistique*. Éditions Gallimard.
4. Hénaut, L., & Salatko, G. (2020). Le devenir des diplômés : Résultats d'une enquête quantitative sur l'emploi des diplômés des quatre formations françaises en conservation-restauration (1975-2018). *Conservation-restauration des biens culturels*, 37, 5-40.
5. Moureau, N., & Sagot-Duvauroux, D. (2010). La nébuleuse des intermédiaires de l'art actuel. In *L'artiste et ses intermédiaires* (p. 55-67). Mardaga, 2010. <https://hal.science/hal-00532820>

From Adaptation to the Context of Monuments to Accounting New Media, Overview of The Evolution of Specialities of Educational Training at The Conservator Department of The National Institute for Heritage in Paris

Amélie Méthivier*, Pauline Chassaing

INP - Institute National du Patrimoine (Paris, France)

*Contact Author: amelie.methivier@inp.fr

The National Heritage Institute (Institut National du Patrimoine: INP) was created through the merger of two distinct institutions: the École Nationale du Patrimoine (ENP), responsible for training civil servant curators, and the Institut Français de Restauration des œuvres d'Art (IFROA), which had existed since 1977 and specialised in training conservator-restorers. The resulting institution is unique in Europe, bringing together two essential professions in the heritage sector.

As a public institution under the direct authority of the French Ministry of Culture, INP falls under the supervision of the Directorate of Heritage and Architecture. Other educational institutions governed by the Ministry of Culture include schools of architecture, art, and cinema.

A Unique Curriculum in Conservation-Restoration

The initial training in conservation-restoration was a four-year program, extended to five years following the Bologna Process. Admission is highly selective and includes a competitive entrance examination assessing knowledge in science, art history, and drawing, followed by manual skill tests specific to the applicant's chosen specialisation. In fact, specialisation begins as early as the entrance exam, with seven fields offered:

- Painting
- Textile
- Photography
- Graphic Arts and Books
- Furniture
- Sculpture
- Fired Arts (ceramics, glass, enamel, and metal)

The degree awarded is recognized as equivalent to a Master's degree, following evaluation by the High Council for the Evaluation of Research and Higher Education (HCERES), similar to university accreditation processes. This recognition enables INP to partake in programs such as Erasmus+.

Legal and Professional Framework

Conservation-restoration in France has deep roots in the museum sector. The 1931 Rome Conference, a milestone in the development of conservation-restoration training, brought together museum directors from across Europe—highlighting the museum-centric origins of the profession.

In France, the legal framework for heritage management is defined by the Code du Patrimoine, which consolidates earlier legislation, including laws pertaining to museums. Among other regulations, it specifies that only professionals with a Master's degree in conservation-restoration may carry out treatments on public collections. This requirement, tied to the designation of "Musée de France," effectively regulates the profession within museums.

Conservators trained at INP are therefore well-prepared for museum environments: working on small to medium-sized, often unique objects, housed in controlled environments with access to archives and research, and in collaboration with curators, registrars, and researchers.

However, this museum focus has historically limited the presence of conservators in other heritage contexts such as historic monuments, archives, libraries, and archaeology—areas where no similar qualification requirements exist.

Expanding to Historic Monuments

Recognizing this gap, the Fédération Française des Conservateurs-Restaurateurs (FFCR) created a working group on historic monuments in 2012. The group engaged with the Heritage and Architecture Directorate to highlight inconsistencies in how legal status affects conservation.

For example, *The Vow of Louis XIII* by Ingres, housed in Montauban Cathedral, is legally less protected than *Ingres' The Dream of Ossian*, located just 300 meters away in the Ingres Museum. This disparity underscores the need for more consistent conservation standards, regardless of whether an artwork remains in situ or has been transferred to a museum.

The FFCR also recognized that the underrepresentation of conservators in historic monument conservation is not solely due to legal gaps but also to educational limitations. Conservators must be trained to address specific challenges, such as large-scale works, structural complexity, and minimal backup services.

For example, a sculpture conservator working in a church must know how to safely remove a piece from a height and develop security measures to prevent theft once the work has been reinstalled.

Collaborative Seminars and Curriculum Reforms

As a result of these reflections, an annual seminar was launched in 2021 for students from all four French Master's-level conservation-restoration programs. The seminar addresses conservation in the context of historic monuments and covers:

- Project definition by architects in collaboration with owners (e.g., city councils or the state)
- Scientific control oversight by the Ministry of Culture
- Public procurement procedures
- Execution and quality control of conservation work

The seminar has taken place in Tours (2021), Paris (2022), Rennes (2023), and will be held in Avignon (2025). It also fosters valuable exchange among students from different training programmes.

At INP, the sculpture department adapted its curriculum to include larger-scale projects. Students now train on-site with altarpieces, learning how to work on scaffolding, handle heavy materials, and follow strict safety protocols, especially regarding lead contamination.

These objects, often stored in damp and poorly monitored locations, suffer from insect damage and structural deterioration—thus generating specific conservation challenges. Sometimes, this work also involves collaboration between the sculpture and furniture sections, as seen in a recent joint project on an altar table from a church in Southern France.

The Need for Mural Painting and Stained-Glass Expertise

There is an alarming shortage of trained professionals in mural painting, exacerbated by the pending retirement of the first generation of conservators trained in the 1970s. While these professionals tend to retire late, the demographic gap remains a critical concern.

INP's painting section has therefore enhanced its training by:

- Introducing first-year on-site workshops focused on diagnostics and condition reporting of wall paintings, in relation to the building's structure.
- Expanding material coverage to include inorganic painting techniques, such as fresco and lime-based methods.
- Teaching key skills like stratigraphic analysis and lime grouting.

In parallel, feedback from the field—especially from the Département de l'Aube, known for its rich stained-glass heritage—highlighted the need for a stained-glass conservation specialisation.

The Cité du Vitrail (International City of Stained Glass) was established to promote and preserve this heritage. It includes exhibition spaces, educational workshops, and a research centre. The regional conservation authority offered dismantled stained-glass panels from endangered churches as practice objects for students.

This partnership convinced INP to add a stained-glass specialisation within the Fired Arts section. This new program opened to applicants in the 2025 entrance exam. Students will benefit from shared first-year training across sub-disciplines, and hands-on practice in facilities adapted to lead-safe treatment.

Embracing the Digital Shift

The latest HCERES evaluation in 2017 recommended that INP strengthen its engagement with digital heritage. The photography section responded by:

- Updating its entrance exam to use digital imaging instead of analogue photography.
- Introducing coursework on digital image conservation, including coding and data preservation.

Initially, the curriculum was heavy on computer science, which puzzled students unfamiliar with its connection to conservation. After internal reflection, the program was restructured to treat the conservator as a project manager—someone who must understand and oversee the preservation of diverse digital media: images, video, sound, or combinations thereof.

Students now receive foundational training in digital heritage and may choose to specialise through a fourth-year international internship and a Master's thesis focused on digital works. For example, one student is currently working on a multimedia artwork in the Centre Pompidou composed of slide projectors, photographs, remote controls, and lighting systems.

Conclusion

The evolution of specialisation at INP illustrates the complexity of adapting heritage education to shifting needs. Whether expanding into underrepresented fields like mural painting, stained glass, or digital heritage, such changes require careful, incremental adjustments—similar in precision and thoughtfulness to the conservation-restoration treatments themselves.

Preserving the Past, Shaping the Future: The Conservator's Landscape in Sweden

Sara Roberts

Studio Västsvensk konservering, SVK (Gothenburg, Sweden)

*Contact Author: sara.roberts@vgregion.se

Keywords: sector needs, heritage policies, professional development, skills gap, training programs, workforce adaptation.

Abstract

Over the past decade, Sweden's conservation-restoration sector has transformed due to evolving heritage policies, increased focus on sustainable preservation, and shifting responsibilities toward public organizations and the building sector. Demand for conservator-restorers, especially in stone, mural, and metal conservation, has surged—yet these areas face acute specialist shortages. The trend toward larger renovation projects, centralization, and rising overheads challenges niche experts and threatens the survival of unique skills. As a result, robust training programs are crucial to ensure a flexible and skilled workforce that can meet evolving sector needs. Educational institutions and companies like SVK play vital roles in addressing these shortages and adapting to industry shifts. Balancing specialist and generalist training is essential to confront increasingly complex conservation challenges across both heritage and museum sectors, securing the future vitality of the profession.

The Conservator Workforce in Sweden: Roles, Distribution, and Structural Dynamics

Over the past decade, the conservation-restoration sector in Sweden has undergone a significant transformation, driven by evolving heritage policies and legislation. With a growing emphasis on sustainable preservation and an increasing transfer of responsibilities to public organisations and the building sector, the focus has shifted from small-scale projects to the large-scale renovation of entire buildings and extensive sculpture collections. As a result, the demand for conservator-restorers has risen, particularly for specialists in stone, mural, and metal conservation—fields currently experiencing a critical shortage in Sweden.

The trend toward centralisation, larger tenders, framework agreements, and rising overhead costs creates considerable challenges for highly specialized or niche conservator-restorers running their own businesses, putting invaluable expertise at risk of disappearing.

In light of these challenges, training programs remain crucial for the profession's survival. To keep pace with the evolving needs of the cultural heritage sector, it is essential to continue educating both specialists and generalists, ensuring a robust and adaptable conservation-restoration workforce.

This presentation examines how the sector can confront these challenges internally, with educational institutions playing a vital role in fostering growth and adaptation. SVK, Sweden's largest conservation-restoration company with more than 20 conservator-restorers covering all cultural heritage specialisations, serves as an illustrative example from the private sector.

The article focuses on the heritage sector's need for conservators-restorers, while also considering the evolving demands of the museum sector. It explores how these two interrelated fields require a balanced combination of specialist and generalist skills to address complex conservation challenges. The discussion highlights current shortages in key specialisations such as stone, mural, and metal conservation, as well as the pressures facing conservators in the heritage sector and the museums due to shifting policies, legislation, and project scale. By examining these perspectives, the article aims to provide insight into future directions for conservation education and professional development that align with the sectors changing needs.

In 2023, the number of members of the Swedish branch of the Nordic Conservators organisation, NKF-S, was 263. The vast majority of these members work as "operational" conservators in museums and in the private market. Approximately 15 conservators are employed within the more administrative parts of the heritage sector, such as at the National Heritage Board, regional administration boards, and at the administration of the Church of Sweden. These individuals hold important roles as stakeholders and policy makers as conservation assignments, legislation and related decisions are ordered, purchased and decided by other heritage specialists than conservators such as archaeologists, art historians, building curators rather than conservators themselves.

Of the around 250 conservators working operationally, about half are employed in museums and the other half work for companies providing conservation services. There are two larger companies, one in Stockholm and another in Gothenburg, supported by a number of smaller firms that often collaborate on larger projects. The work force is primarily concentrated in the major cities and southern Sweden, leaving significant parts of the country with limited access to conservation expertise.

Conservators working in museums generally focus on collection management, emphasising on preventive conservation, while only scarcely engaging in curative treatments within their specialisation.

Conservators in private practice generally focus on applied conservation and restoration, working either in their studios or on site. Their clients typically include private owners, developers, public sector administrators of art or cultural properties, as well as museums.

Trends in Conservation and Restoration in Sweden

We observe several positive trends in the handling and ownership of art, buildings, and the heritage sector in Sweden.

Legislation

The Museums Act [1], which came into force in 2017, is the first comprehensive legislation for the museum sector in Sweden. It governs qualitative aspects of museum activities, including knowledge development, public engagement, collection management, cooperation, and the allocation of roles. Museums are tasked with the responsibility to acquire, preserve, and care for their collections as an integral part of safeguarding cultural heritage. The primary purpose of the Museums Act is to ensure that museums maintain an active societal role by preserving and developing cultural heritage, promoting knowledge, and offering cultural experiences accessible to all.

The Policy for a Designed Living Environment [2] was adopted in Sweden in 2018. Inspired by frameworks such as the United Nations' *New Urban Agenda* and *the New European Bauhaus*, the policy emphasises the importance of architecture, design, art, and the cultural environment in shaping a sustainable and inclusive living environment. It highlights the value of co-creation processes and encompasses architecture, design, art, and cultural heritage. Moreover, it encourages stakeholders, owners, and caretakers to strengthen their efforts in preserving both tangible and intangible cultural heritage.

Evolving Priorities

Since 2000, The Church of Sweden has received annual financial support to fulfil its responsibility for maintenance and preservation of church buildings, churchyards, interiors, and furnishings, including objects such as textiles, metals and paintings. The cultural and historical values of these churches must be preserved, and high-quality standards are required for all repairs, care, maintenance, and modifications. The Church of Sweden collaborates closely with heritage conservation authorities to find solutions that balance preservation with the need for necessary changes. During the first two decades, the focus was primarily on structural maintenance, including energy savings, upgrading climate systems, and weatherproofing roofs, windows and walls. Now that those essential tasks have been largely completed, attention is increasingly turning to restoration works on the surface layers of the buildings, as well as on the interiors and historic objects.

Energy Efficiency Integration

Large-scale renovations increasingly incorporate energy efficiency measures, reflecting their growing importance in both the building process and in the broader construction industry. This trend challenges conservators to balance historical preservation with modern sustainability requirements, stimulating demand for their specialised expertise.

Material Reuse

The emphasis on sustainability has also led to a stronger focus on reusing building materials, especially in large-scale renovations. This development impacts the conservation field by requiring skills in identifying, preserving, and repurposing historical materials. Conservators are becoming crucial advisors in deciding when and how to retain original structures within renovation projects, aligning heritage preservation with environmental goals.

Digitalisation and Documentation

There is a growing importance of digital technologies for documenting, managing, and sharing heritage information. This includes 3D scanning, digital archiving, and virtual access to collections and cultural sites. Digital tools enhance conservation planning, risk assessment, and public engagement with heritage.

Community and Stakeholder Involvement

Increasingly, heritage management includes participatory approaches, engaging local communities, and a broader range of stakeholders in decision-making processes. This participatory governance model helps align conservation efforts with societal values and promotes shared stewardship.

Challenges in the Sector

As for challenges in the sector, the job market for operational conservators in Sweden is currently vulnerable and weak, although there are signs of positive change on the horizon.

As noted earlier, the number of professional conservators is very limited, and growth in the field has been slow or stagnant [3]. Student enrolment in conservation and restoration programs has historically been low but has shown a modest but promising increase in recent years. The master's program has primarily attracted international students, many of whom return to their home countries after graduation; however, this also reflects a small yet positive trend toward increased interest domestically.

Geographically, the market is uneven: some regions suffer from a shortage of jobs, while others face a scarcity of conservators. For example, northern Sweden has very few conservation and restoration experts, making it difficult for heritage institutions to hire qualified professionals. Consequently, other workers such as craftsmen often perform conservation tasks in these areas.

With rising interest and growing needs for conservation, restoration and heritage preservation, it is critical to ensure that the profession can meet future demands. Increasing the number of trained conservators is essential to avoid other disciplines taking over conservation responsibilities due to lack of available expertise.

Bridging Knowledge and Practice

Since the founding of the Department of Conservation at the University of Gothenburg, there has been a strong partnership with professionals in the conservation sector. This collaboration is essential for students, providing them with opportunities to apply theoretical knowledge in real-world settings. More broadly, close cooperation between universities and practitioners is crucial everywhere, ensuring effective integration of academic learning and professional practice across the entire field.

Construction Business and Public Tenders

Over the last five to ten years, conservators in Sweden have faced increasing demands to take on responsibilities as general contractors in large, complex building projects. The use of public tenders has grown, and legislation concerning health and safety has been stringent. These developments require conservators to acquire new knowledge, education and competencies, as well as to allocate more time and financial resources to these additional tasks. This increased overhead can place smaller conservation companies at a competitive disadvantage in tender processes.

Moreover, the rising demand for conservation work within the construction sector has amplified the need for specialists in metal and stone conservation — areas where Sweden currently experiences a shortage of qualified experts.

The Right Person in the Right Place

On an organisational level, particularly within the political and administrative sides of cultural heritage management, there is a notable shortage of conservators. Tasks such as formulating guidelines and manuals, clarifying implementation of legislation related to heritage preservation, conservation and restoration, and supervising conservation work are often handled by professionals from other fields.

With the rise in public tenders and procurements in the heritage sector, the need for professional knowledge about when to hire conservators and how to specify precise criteria for conservation work has become critical. Currently these roles are mostly filled by non-conservators who define, demand, and purchase conservation services without adequate understanding of the work involved or proper evaluation methods for bids [4]. This often results in procurement decisions being driven solely by price rather than quality, putting conservation outcomes at risk.

The Swedish National Heritage Board

From the 1970s to the 1990s the Swedish National Heritage Board, Riksantikvarieämbetet, was a strong and well-resourced state organisation with a staff of 25 to 30 conservators across all specialisations. It operated large-scale facilities connected with the National Historical Museum in Stockholm and provided both contract conservation and conservation services for public museums, public art, and churches. During this period, the Swedish National Heritage Board led major state-funded research projects on environmental impacts affecting built heritage and archaeological objects. The conservation unit was a respected and influential actor in political and regulatory circles. This period highlights a time when state financed conservation was deeply integrated into cultural

heritage governance, supported by strong research initiatives and a broad conservation team actively involved across multiple sectors.

However, since its relocation to Gotland in 2005/2006, the Swedish National Heritage Board's visibility and direct influence in politics and regulation have diminished significantly compared to its earlier prominence. The move marked a shift in the organisational dynamics of heritage conservation within Sweden. Today, the organisation's role and influence have evolved, reflecting wider changes in the heritage sector and its governance.

Sweden no longer has a national knowledge centre dedicated specifically to heritage and conservation. This absence means there is currently no single authoritative body to promote and advocate for conservation within the cultural heritage sector. While organisations like the Swedish National Heritage Board have departments supporting heritage development and conservation science, a dedicated, centralised centre explicitly championing conservation as a profession and practice is missing at the national level. This gap challenges the sector's capacity to coordinate, represent, and advance conservation needs and priorities effectively.

Education and Specialisation in Conservation in Sweden

The Department of Conservation at the University of Gothenburg offers the only conservation and restoration education program in Sweden. The program provides students with a broad foundation in conservation principles and the treatment of diverse materials. At the undergraduate (BSc) level, students have the opportunity to specialise in their third year by selecting a focus area for both their internship and thesis project. At the master's (MSc) level, the University offers more highly targeted and in-depth expertise, allowing students to specialise in areas such as conservation of cultural heritage objects. The master's program integrates science, practical conservation, as well as research, and is designed to develop both methodological and technical skills alongside critical thinking. It is taught by experienced conservators and incorporates international standards, preparing graduates for professional work both within Sweden and globally. Since its inception in 1984, and until the introduction of the MSc program 2020, the Department of Conservation at the University of Gothenburg only offered a BSc education in conservation. This program provided a broad conservation education during the first two years, covering a wide range of materials and adopting a broad, generalist approach. In the third year, students specialised in one of several areas, which varied according to a set schedule. Typical specialisations included paintings conservation, textiles and paper, objects and archaeology. During the early 1990s, natural history/taxidermy was also offered.

Throughout the 1990s and 2000s one of the specialisations was "Conservation of cultural heritage objects" which emphasized collection management, preventive conservation, and provided broad knowledge and skills in applied conservation across various materials and objects. This specialisation forms an important part of the department's legacy, as the majority of conservator-restorers currently working in Sweden were educated within this system. This foundation has deeply influenced the conservation profession in the country, with many practitioners possessing wide-ranging expertise grounded in this comprehensive educational model.

Since the introduction and start of the International MSc education in 2020, the BSc program has become less specialised. During the BSc program, students may choose their specialisation in the third year from several available options. The MSc program offers a defined specialisation, which may vary over time. Since the start of the MSc programme the offered specialisations have included:

- 2019, 2020 – Paintings
- 2021, 2022 – Modern materials
- 2023 – Textile
- 2024 – Archaeological materials
- 2025 – no student intake
- 2026 – Stone & mural paintings

Both degree programs incorporate structured internship periods that provide students with valuable practical experience in real-world conservation settings. These internships allow students to apply theoretical knowledge, develop hands-on skills, and engage directly with conservation projects under professional supervision. For BSc students, the internship typically lasts 15 weeks and is followed by theoretical coursework during their third year. This extended placement offers an immersive experience where students can develop broad practical competencies across a range of materials and conservation tasks.

MSc students dedicate the entire first semester of their second year (20 weeks) to an internship within their speciality. They also complete a dedicated course in the specialisation they have chosen. This longer, focused placement enables them to deepen their expertise within their chosen field by working on complex or specialised projects, and by building professional networks in the conservation sector.

Together, these internships form a critical component of the education programs, bridging academic learning with professional practice and preparing students for future careers in conservation.

Furthermore, the education incorporates study tours and actively encourages interaction with established professionals in the conservation field. These components help students gain broader perspectives and foster valuable professional networks early in their careers. Such engagement is crucial not only for applying theoretical knowledge but also for connecting students with their future labour market.

Hands-on practice is widely regarded as the most effective way to acquire and deepen conservation skills. Even brief work placements can have a significant and meaningful impact on a student's development. Direct exposure to professional environments, combined with opportunities to learn from experienced practitioners, greatly enriches the educational experience. This practical engagement prepares future conservators for the specialised and complex nature of conservation work they will encounter in their careers.

Generalists and Specialists

Conservation is indeed a highly complex and multifaceted profession that requires a broad but often tailored skill set. It demands both breadth and depth of expertise, grounded in practical experience and a commitment to continuous learning. To what extent the depth of specialised training influences the level of competences is not an easy question to answer. Conservation work involves various parameters, including material specialisations, object types, institutional contexts and the diverse demands of clients, which can be shaped by legislation, business models, and other factors.

A wall painting in a church might have been created at the same time, with the same materials, and exhibit similar types of damage requiring comparable treatment as a wall painting in a historic house. However, differences in ownership, legislation, and political context can lead to significant variations in how the conservation treatment is handled. This affects the decision-making process, project planning and the level of documentation required, making each case unique despite the technical similarities.

The need for specialists and generalists varies depending on the situation. In heritage institutions—such as galleries, libraries, archives, and museums—and in private practice, the requirements for specialisation differ according to the institution's focus and size, as well as the nature and scale of the practice. For example, a smaller local museum with mixed collections may require conservators with broader, more generalist skills, while a large art museum with a primary focus on classic or contemporary art works demands highly specialised expertise. Similarly, a small, one-person private practice may function primarily as a generalist service provider, in contrast to larger, more specialised practices like Studio Västsvensk Konservering.

All these variables must be carefully considered when engaging with an object and its owner, making each conservation situation unique and requiring adaptable expertise.

Generalists

A generalist in the conservation field possesses comprehensive knowledge and practical experience working with a wide range of materials. This expertise enables the conservator to work with mixed collections, assess a wide range of conservation needs, and coordinate care and preventive measures. This individual might serve as a collection manager at a museum, maintaining an overall understanding of the collections and their environments. While capable of performing applied conservation work on most of the objects, the generalist will defer specialists when delicate or highly specialised treatments are required. In this context, being a generalist is a specialisation, as they play a crucial role in identifying the need for specialist intervention and effectively purchasing those services.

Specialists

In contrast, a specialist builds upon this broad foundation by dedicating focused expertise and hands-on proficiency to a specific area - such as the conservation of paintings, textiles, or archaeological artifacts. A specialist applies advanced techniques and detailed understanding to complex, sensitive,

or high-value objects, ensuring treatments are precisely tailored and effective. While specialisation typically develops over many years of practice, having a strong foundation rooted in practical training and real-world experience is essential to professional growth in this complex and constantly evolving field.

Both types of expertise rely on practical experience, which builds the hands-on skills and intuitive judgment vital for successful conservation work. The nuanced conditions of each object and situation cannot be fully captured in theory alone. A common basic level of general knowledge across specialisation levels – such as preventive conservation, handling, packing, and environmental control – is crucial. This foundational knowledge provides a shared language and understanding within the profession, enabling conservators to collaborate effectively. It also lays the groundwork for deepening expertise and advancing the quality of conservation work throughout their careers.

Moreover, conservation is a constantly evolving discipline, influenced by new research, materials science advancements, and changing ethical and regulatory frameworks. Therefore, continuous learning is essential for both generalists and specialists to keep their knowledge up to date, refine techniques, and adapt to emerging challenges.

In summary, conservation requires a balance of both breadth and depth of expertise, supported by practical experience and ongoing learning. The sector depends on highly specialised professionals who possess deep knowledge in specific areas, as well as generalist professionals who have a broad understanding of various materials and a versatile approach. This combination ensures comprehensive care and effective preservation of cultural heritage across diverse contexts and challenges.

What Does the Sector Need?

I will pause for a moment to reflect on one of the key questions addressed in the conference theme: What does the sector need? What exactly is “the sector”, and who determines its needs? Who or what drives the demand for conservation and restoration? How does this demand fluctuate over time? And what influence can conservators and restorers have in shaping or redirecting the sector’s demands?

I also consider the difference between what the sector truly needs and what it wants. To simplify, if we define the sector as the overall cultural heritage sector in Sweden, I believe the situation would be quite different if more conservators were involved in the administration of this sector. Currently, the administrators in the sector are largely not conservators, so how can they fully understand what the sector needs and how those needs should be addressed, particularly regarding conservation and restoration? I therefore see a need for a different kind of specialisation: the conservator as a decision maker, a purchaser, a museum director, or even the head of a national heritage organisation. My concern is that the conservation field often places too much emphasis on technical aspects, and I believe we should give greater attention to discussions about ethics, theory, and — most importantly — the questions of why we conserve and for whom.

Conservation is not solely about material science and chemistry; it also encompasses politics, legislation, and heritage management. In many ways, conservation is the cultural heritage sector

itself. We should ask: Who requests the conservator's expertise? Who ought to request it? And who is truly qualified to determine when a conservator's involvement is necessary? These are critical questions for shaping the future direction and relevance of the conservation profession.

Educational programs could and should encourage these that explore the theoretical, ethical, and philosophical aspects of conservation, as emphasised by Caroline Owman [5].

This broader approach enriches the profession by fostering critical reflection on the reasons behind conservation practices and the values they uphold, complementing the technical skills traditionally prioritised in training.

Addressing the Sector's Needs – A Case Study

In 2024, a team of 21 conservators worked across nine different specialisations at Studio Västsvensk Konservering (SVK), supported by one administrative staff member and one manager. The studio's scope covers collections in museums, archives and libraries, as well as art both indoors and outdoors. Their work also extends to built heritage, projects for the Church of Sweden, and the contract archaeology sector.

Clients include a broad range of stakeholders such as state authorities, regional bodies, municipalities and cities, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), associations, private owners of buildings and art collections, and individual private clients. The Studio engages in both preventive conservation and curative treatment, applying a wide variety of methods tailored to the diverse needs of their clients and projects.

SVK's major advantage lies in the diversity of specialisations housed under one roof. This broad range of expertise makes the organisation exceptionally flexible, allowing conservators to collaborate across disciplines and support each other on projects that extend beyond their primary areas of focus.

Many project tasks are quite general in nature—such as cleaning, surface coating, and other routine treatments—that do not always require highly specialised expertise. Additionally, SVK often undertakes large-scale initiatives, including mould cleaning, comprehensive collection inventories, and storage management. SVK also performs inventories, develops maintenance plans, and creates collection management plans, alongside conducting risk assessments to ensure the ongoing care and preservation of cultural heritage collections.

In these contexts, a strong background in collection management, health and safety protocols, conservation ethics, object handling, storage and packing techniques, and systematic workflow is often more valuable than in-depth knowledge of a specific material or technique.

At SVK, professional development for newly qualified conservators typically requires about two years of hands-on training to become a fully independent project manager. During the first year, the focus is on mastering essential skills—methods, techniques, routines, reporting standards, and more. New conservators usually work within the projects of senior colleagues under direct supervision, dedicating

this time exclusively to learning without holding internal responsibilities. In the second year, they start managing smaller projects independently, which involves tasks like time and cost estimation.

SVK places little emphasis on whether a conservator holds a Bachelor's (BSc) or Master's (MSc) degree. Instead, what truly matters are the individual's skills, craftsmanship, attitude, prior experiences, and personal qualities. Often, these factors have a much greater impact on a conservator's success after two years of training at SVK than the formal level of education. Accumulated work experience — especially during the first two to five years after qualification — combined with personal skills and areas of specialisation, is essential to a conservator's professional growth and future success. True specialisation in conservation typically develops gradually throughout one's career. The early years following qualification serve as a crucial formative period, establishing a broad foundation of skills and knowledge. As conservators gain experience facing diverse challenges and exploring various areas of interest, their expertise becomes increasingly focused and refined, enabling them to develop true specialisation over time.

The Importance of Lifelong Learning and Research Literacy

It is essential for conservators to stay informed about the latest research and technological advances in their field. Lifelong learning and active engagement with research and development resources are vital for maintaining high standards in conservation practice. Although opportunities for conducting original research may be limited at SVK — as the organisation does not perform any extensive material analyses nor frequently participates in research projects— it remains crucial to keep up to date with current developments and know where to seek specialised analyses when necessary. SVK fosters this ongoing exchange of knowledge by attending conferences, organising workshops and courses both for its staff and the wider conservation community, and hosting interns from national and international universities. These activities ensure a continual influx of new knowledge and perspectives, enriching the operational competence of the organisation and helping conservators stay connected to advances and innovations in the field.

Soft Skills – More than Technical Specialisations

Key traits for success in our diverse conservation practice—where project types and object categories vary widely — include flexibility, sound decision-making, strong problem-solving abilities, creativity, imagination, and effective communication skills. Additionally, prior life experience can contribute significantly to a conservator's capability to navigate complex and varied challenges.

To prepare students for professional life, it is essential to equip them with practical skills beyond conservation techniques, including project management, sales, and business acumen. These skills help future conservators manage projects efficiently, engage with clients, and contribute to the sustainability of their practice.

As employers, we carry a significant responsibility to support our employees in acquiring and deepening this knowledge. This involves providing opportunities for ongoing professional development, facilitating access to training and resources, and creating an environment where staff

can immerse themselves fully in learning and growth. By doing so, we ensure both individual career progression and the overall strength and adaptability of the organisation.

A Call to Action

I would like to conclude with a call to action for the conservation community, urging professionals, educators, and policymakers to work collaboratively to expand and strengthen the conservation profession, asking critical questions: For whom do we conserve, and why? To better understand these developments, the following key points highlight the main aspects and implications of the situation:

The Profession:

- Conservators should have the authority to decide when a conservation-restoration intervention is needed.
- Clarify professional roles and work to change how others perceive conservators.
- Take up roles in decision-making positions and within administrative structures.

The Education:

- Align the number of graduates with the sector's actual needs.
- Continue the excellent work of educating both generalists and specialists in conservation-restoration.
- Increase student enrolment and graduation rates.
- Inspire and attract students to careers not only in conservation practice but also in heritage administration

For Whom and Why?

- We need to respond and adapt to the needs of the heritage and museum sectors.
- Gain a deep understanding of, and communicate effectively about, legislation, politics, and the heritage system.
- Speak the languages of related fields such as archaeology, architecture, city planning, environmental processes, art history, and theology.
- Clearly declare the purpose of conservation-restoration — it is not just science and chemistry, but a multidisciplinary practice rooted in cultural, political, and ethical frameworks.

The sector's need for conservators and restorers is continually evolving, presenting a challenge for education providers to keep pace with or even anticipate these changes. Educational programs must maintain a clear focus on defining what conservation truly is and why it is undertaken. It is essential to develop the capacity for meaningful dialogue and to respond effectively to the changing needs of the cultural heritage sector, thereby raising awareness of conservation's importance - even within the heritage sector itself.

Therefore, it is crucial for educational institutions to maintain close collaboration with practicing conservation professionals while staying informed about political and legislative trends affecting the sector. This integrated approach ensures that conservation education remains relevant, adaptive, and responsive to the future demands of the profession.

There is no need to change the definition of conservation. Rather, we need to change how we speak about conservation—from focusing primarily on materials, chemistry, and the technical aspects of what we do, to emphasising *why* we do it. Conservation is not just about hands-on treatments of objects. It encompasses soft skills, professional judgment, decision-making, politics, and broader cultural and societal contexts. Only the conservation-restoration profession and education can change the current perception and system. To achieve this, we must make alliances and build strong connections between education providers and professionals.

References

1. *Museilag* (2017:563). https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-och-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/museilag-2017563_sfs-2017-563/
2. *Politik för en gestaltad livsmiljö* (prop. 2017/18:110). <https://www.regeringen.se/contentassets/8ecb8b5973924e6b9e93627c041d27a6/politik-for-gestaltad-livsmiljo-prop.-201718110.pdf>
3. Jensen, O.W. (2019) *Kompetenser med konsekvenser för kulturmiljö- och museisektorn: en förstudie*. Stockholm: Riksantikvarieämbetet, p 18-19. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1387382/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
4. NKF-S (2015). *Remissvar – Riksantikvarieämbetets rapport Översyn av regelverket om de kyrkliga kulturminnena* (Dnr: Ku2015/02346/KL). <https://www.regeringen.se/contentassets/05boobeaa31aa46ee83ca63188b8bfc94/nordiska-konservatorforbundet-.pdf>
5. Owman, C. (2021). *Det meränmänskliga museet: Konservatorns bevarandepraktik som flyktlinje i modernitetens museum*. [Doctoral Thesis]. Umeå universitet, Humanistiska fakulteten, Institutionen för kultur- och medievvetenskaper. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1589328/FULLTEXT01.pdf>

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